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“Design of Communicative B2-level CLIL didactic materials as a resource in English History Classes of adult language students from Paraná, Argentina”

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1. INTRODUCTION

CLIL is an approach in which a “foreign language is used as a tool in the learning of a non-language subject in which both, language and subject have a joint role”. (Marsh, 2002, p.58). Furthermore, CLIL is “an umbrella term covering a dozen or more educational approaches such as Immersion, bilingual education, multilingual education, and more” (García, 2013, p.49). With this in mind, it may be said that there is not one specific or unique version of CLIL, neither a particular methodology in which it should be carried out. In today’s world, even now CLIL demands training for teachers, as there is an apparent absence of marketed course books, for that reason teachers usually have to become creators of their own materials in order to use the English language on an everyday basis or in other subjects of the curriculum, particularly in tertiary education.

During the master’s program at Funiber students were asked to study Content and Language Learning Integrated Learning (CLIL), which has gained popularity all over Europe. It came to my mind that it could be an effective tool for teaching English History at an undergraduate course of adult language students with a B2-level of English proficiency according to the Common European Framework of English. In designing material that follows a CLIL methodology, there are some elements of both language and subject teaching/learning which will surely come into light, these of course are specific to the CLIL classroom along with up-and-coming CLIL methodologies. The reasons for the popularity of the CLIL methodology in Europe are evident, as using a specific language as the medium of instruction is believed to result in “naturalistic language learning”, facilitate meaningful language use and thus reduce target language anxiety and boost motivation (Dalton-Puffer & Smit, 2007). Research results on student achievement are mostly positive as well. As regards to content learning, CLIL students are generally found to possess knowledge and skills equal to their non-CLIL counterparts (Dalton-Puffer, 2009), even outperforming them in learning certain topics.

Although positive experiences abound in CLIL literature, there are reports however, about their lack of context-responsive activities which are highly demanded in today’s market. Over the last few years, there has been a great increase among educational institutions adopting CLIL materials to satisfy students’ needs. However, few of those materials are designed for English History lessons or other subjects. By designing activities which focus on teaching English History’s main themes and topics by means of a second language with simultaneous aims, specifically the learning of content and the

parallel learning of a second language, students may be able to better their understanding of some of this subject's most relevant contents. Consequently, this thesis is based on the design and applicability of CLIL materials to test their efficacy for foreign language learners in Paraná, Entre Ríos, Argentina, to improve their learning of English History at a tertiary level.

The design and implementation of these CLIL didactic materials is based on a Communicative approach, also taking into account several important aspects, such as the communicative skills of the learners, the use of CLIL didactic materials in the classroom, EFL material design, assessment of students' performance, and the outcomes from the implementation of those CLIL materials in English History classes.

Having clarified the aim of this paper and the elements the design didactic materials will take into account; I would like to specify some of the main topics which will be covered in this paper as well as its organization. Firstly, I will justify and explain my academic and personal interest in this topic, then I will mention the general as well as the specific objectives of this paper, making reference to CLIL, the students' needs, as well as the possible challenges of the design of the CLIL materials mentioned. After that I will develop what is Communicative Language Teaching and what it entails, I will also cover how CLIL didactic materials are designed and how they can be implemented in the subject of English History, and finally, I will assess and mention the possible outcomes of the implementation of the materials mentioned above.

2. JUSTIFICATION OF ACADEMIC AND PERSONAL INTEREST

As a professor of English History and English Language at “New Start”, a tertiary institution where students study to become teachers of English as a second language and English translators, I have encountered some problems with my first-year students. The majority of these students have a low level of English proficiency, as a result, they have problems understanding the subject’s contents. Despite the increasingly popular Content and Language Integrated Learning experiences in primary and secondary institutions in European countries, there is not enough research on the use of CLIL in Higher Education. For these reasons, I’ve decided to design and implement CLIL (which involves teaching students about a subject in a foreign language). I have decided to develop this final project because I believe it will help English History teachers with students without enough proficiency in the English language by using these resources in their classes. In this case, I will be taking into account the contents taught in the subject English Language, which is key for students in their first-year, since it takes into account skills such as reading, speaking, writing, listening and overall use of English in the B2 level of English according to the Common European Framework of Reference.

Several authors consider materials:

a central aspect in foreign instruction and a decisive element within the relationship between teacher, learner and foreign language acquisition. For that reason, teachers must have a large range of materials available. other than traditional resources (blackboard, textbook, flashcards, puppets, etc.), there are many activities implying songs, tales, etc. which can also be done with audio-visual materials such as the interactive whiteboard and internet to foster the acquisition of linguistic competence and help teachers enrich the students’ communicative skill in an entertaining and motivating way. (Trujillo, Torrecillas y Salvadores, 2004, p.409)

Coyle et al. (2010) maintains that teaching CLIL implicates well-organized materials which are cognitively challenging for students, and also providing valuable scaffolding. Many of these students become demotivated and some of them “drop out” and quit trying to understand the subject because they lack the necessary knowledge to understand the English History contents, which involve a lot of reading, watching documentaries, discussing as well as carrying out oral presentations of different topics. As a result, it is expected that the students who will use the designed materials not only improve their

English and learn about English History, but also become more motivated, enjoy the subject with its materials and engage in communicative activities which foster their sociolinguistic competence.

This project may help other teachers and students notice how learning content through CLIL tools and techniques may be beneficial for them, and in turn, they might consider implementing CLIL techniques and didactic materials in their own courses. CLIL is still a new teaching method which hasn't been studied as extensively as other teaching methods such as TBL. For that reason, this project may contribute to the study and implementation of CLIL by others in the research field. Moreover, teachers of other subjects, such as English Literature, might find this approach helpful to adopt in their own subjects, as well as English History teachers who may cater from the didactic materials designed in this project.

The design of this material is expected to benefit my English History classes as well as my students. I expect the implementation of the materials designed will become an advantage for future English History courses, in which I will also adopt these materials throughout the years with the aim of not only helping students' understanding of the subject, but also making the study and use of these materials entertaining and resourceful for them in other subjects. Hopefully, by seeing the benefits of CLIL, other teachers will become encouraged to design their own CLIL materials to use with their students as well as share them with other teachers in their community. Overall, I expect they will commit fewer grammatical mistakes in their writing, adopt a broader vocabulary and better their understanding in their reading. I mention these expectations specifically, because these are the main problems I have encountered in this particular group of students; however, this may vary with other groups.

3. OBJECTIVES

The main aim of this paper is to design communicative B2-level CLIL didactic materials which help adult foreign language learners in Paraná, Argentina, with their performance in English History classes. This CLIL materials should aid students in their search to expand their linguistic and subject-specific knowledge and competences in order to be considered effective. It also should bridge learning to a growing intercultural recognition of the subject they are exploring, this is expected to be achieved when implementing this material as a resource during the English History classes.

Another objective of this paper is to design these materials based on the key contents of the subject English Language to implement them as a resource and aid in my current English History lessons in “New Start”. Some of the Grammar contents students encounter in their English Language lessons at the institution are comparatives and superlatives, past, present and future tenses, general and specific vocabulary, etc. Moreover, during the year they are expected to pass a variety of exams which aim to test their listening, reading, writing and speaking skills. These exams are similar to the ones given by the ESOL examinations from Cambridge University. Most students present problems in the use of English and grammar examinations. Regarding the most important topics from the English History subject, I will be focusing on the Tudors, the Stuarts, the Industrial Revolution, The Victorian Age and similar topics which are key in the study of English History. I hope the utilization of those materials as resources within the classroom will provide samples of how subjects which employ the CLIL methodology can motivate and encourage learners to learn content and obtain linguistic skills in a second language by means of utilizing engaging materials. This should be done taking into account tasks which progressively challenge students cognitively and also demands exploration of content and language, both individually and in collaboration with other students.

Because of the fact mentioned above, another objective of this paper is to design the materials considering the students’ needs and how the designed CLIL materials may affect those students’ performance positively or negatively in class. CLIL materials, thanks to their socio-constructivist roots, are inclined to be focused on the students, who are required to take a more active role and be involved in and liable for their own learning process. Thus, knowledge is not fixed, top-down and unknown to learners, however, it is

a developing, everchanging point of view of the world which also possesses the ability to be investigated and changed.

Students become aware of previous knowledge and information while working on a variety of tasks, this can also take place when they investigate, ask questions and use a wide variety of resources to complete certain tasks. By creating materials that motivate students in meaningful exchanges which lead them towards transformation and appropriation, teachers create instances where there is potential learning. As a result, another objective of this paper is to design communicative B2-level CLIL materials that may benefit those students who aren't proficient enough in their second language and consequently, encounter problems in English History classes. This in turn, will help the percentage of students dropping out of the course to decrease, as well as students feeling more comfortable with their linguistic knowledge and enjoying the subjects during their career.

4. THEORETICAL BACKGROUND

4.1 TEFL and Communicative Language Teaching

The growing need for good communication skills in English has created a huge demand for English teaching around the world that tackles this predicament. Many people nowadays want to make their command of English better or be sure that their children will improve on their own abilities. Furthermore, there are plenty of varied opportunities to learn English such as formal instruction, exchange programs, travel, as well as through the Internet or social media. Quality language teaching, as well as materials and resources, are in high demand. The search for an appropriate teaching methodology as well as material is therefore key to meet such demand.

The nature and spirit of English teaching and learning is communication. Teaching and learning are the embodiment of communication between the teacher and students. It's a bilateral activity, the results of which isn't decided by one side but by mutual efforts. So, in a sense, teaching is in communication. As Liu (2015, p.2) states, "focusing on communication, teaching is an activity through which the students acquire linguistic knowledge and form communicative competence". Teaching is through communication.

However, it should be borne in mind that language acquisition is a dynamic process of the communicative and linguistic competence of the learner. Liu (2015, p.2) further explains that the "Dynamic process of language learning depends, to large extent, on the involvement of the learners who are thinking beings, emotional beings and communicators instead of knowledge receptacles".

Taking into consideration what has been said above, there is one methodology present in most classrooms nowadays: Communicative Language Teaching. Richards (2001, p.4) defines it as a "set of principles about the goals of instruction, how learners learn a language, the forms of classroom activities that best facilitate learning, and also the roles of teachers and learners within the classroom". In line with Sanders (1987), it refers to any approach to instruction which emphasizes the meaning and use, instead of the shape of language and which aims at developing the learner's communicative competence in foreign instruction and learning. According to Hymes (1972), communicative competence consists of 4 aspects: possibility, feasibility, appropriateness and performance. This would mean that students should be able to

produce grammatically correct sentences which can be understood, as well as use correct forms of language for specific socio-cultural context, and finally be able to make complete utterances.

4.2 CLT and the shift from grammatical to communicative competence

Language teaching is much more than the teaching of grammar but rather to tell the learners the way to apply “the rules” into practice or to develop the learners’ ability to use the language to speak idiomatically. Perhaps this is often best explained if we take a glance at the concept of grammatical competence and communicative competence.

Grammatical competence per Richards (2001, p.7) refers to “the knowledge we have of a language that accounts for our ability to produce sentences in a language”. In this sense, this competence takes into account the knowledge students have about parts of speech, tenses, phrases, sentence patterns and clauses apart from how sentences are formed. When we talk about grammatical competence, many associate the term with grammar practice books, which are filled with rules and tasks to practice said rules. However, by focusing only on grammatical competence we leave aside the actual use of the language. Students would be able to form sentences but will probably fail at expressing themselves successfully in conversation or having meaningful communication with others. Grammatical competence was mainly present in early methodologies of language teaching, which emphasized the view of language as a process of mechanical formation of habits. The production of well-formed sentences was encouraged, while making mistakes was frowned upon. Memorization and the performance of drills with the teacher as the controller, were viewed as key to further develop the grammatical competence of learners.

Communicative competence, on the other hand, focuses on how the language is used for different purposes and functions. Students are able to communicate with each other despite having limitations in their language knowledge, this is because of their learning and development of a variety of communication strategies. This competence also takes into account how students vary their use of language according to the context and the participants, such as their vocabulary in formal and informal settings. As well as being able to understand different situations in daily life communication, by developing their communicative competence students are able to understand different types of texts as well. Such competence has increasingly become popular in today’s classrooms, where teachers place importance in the negotiation of meaning, experimenting with different

ways of saying the same thing, collaborative creation of meaning, the creation of meaningful and purposeful interaction through language and asking students to pay attention to the feedback they get when using the language. Moreover, according to Liu (2015, p. 2) traditional teaching approaches “emphasized on the forms of sentences as its major purpose for teaching, however, the theory of the communicative method of teaching pays much more attention to the context.”

Perhaps we can best summarize what has been discussed by looking at what Richards (2001, p.5) explains about CLT and communicative competence:

With CLT began a movement away from traditional lesson formats where the focus was on mastery of different items of grammar and practice through controlled activities such as memorization of dialogs and drills, and toward the use of pair work activities, role plays, group work activities and project work.

4.3 The Development of the Communicative Skills

For an English teacher, “A CMT class should be a process of motivating, activating and triggering learners’ internal learning mechanisms” Liu (2015, p. 2). According to Moss and Ross-Feldman (2003), any activity which requires the learner to speak and listen to others includes the use of communication. Some of the main objectives within activities with communicative purposes, is to contribute to breaking down barriers, finding information, expressing ideas about oneself and learning about culture.

Jeyasala (2014) considers that educators ought to encourage students’ communicative competence continually, and aside from their limitations to use language in a fluent and accurate manner, they should make spaces available to them to interact with others or to immerse them in speaking activities which in turn enhance their ability to use the target language.

One of the best options for teachers to improve student’s communicative skills is to provide students with real communicative contexts, because students can exchange real information, so language and phrases will emerge according to the situation. It should also be considered that students have a lot of exposure to the language, so the linguistic input they receive should provide them with opportunities to produce and use the language in any situation. As a result, motivation plays a very important role in encouraging students to verbally communicate.

Richards and Rodgers (2014) list three elements of the learning theory that can be distinguished in some communicative language teaching practices. The first element is that the communication principle that relates to the activities focused on the utilization of real communication. The second is that the task principle which focuses on the employment of language to hold out meaningful tasks. Finally, the third one is that the meaningfulness principle during which the language used must be meaningful to the learner.

There's an excellent number of activities aimed toward developing learners' communicative skills using communicative processes, like information sharing, negotiation of meaning, and interaction. Furthermore, by employing games, role plays, simulations of real-life situations, and task-based communication activities, teachers support classes in which the Communicative language teaching approach is used (Richards and Rodgers, 2014).

Another aspect to take into consideration when trying to develop the communication skills of learners is interaction, which plays a crucial role in acquisition since it gives them the chance to put into practice their communication skills. In order to make meaningful interaction among learners, the right materials that promote such interaction need to be chosen and sometimes even designed by teachers themselves. Richards (2001) states that materials are the key element in learning whether they are textbooks, materials provided by an establishment or materials made by the trainer. Of these materials have the aim of providing students with the foundation for the language practice students receive within the classroom.

Moreover, incorporating authentic materials such as the use of audio-visual material will offer a richer contribution to learners which can be exploited in different ways and levels to improve their communication skills. These authentic materials can be paired up with a communicative practice, which according to Richards (2001, p.13) refers to activities "where practice in using language within a real communicative context is the focus, where real information is exchanged, and where the language used is not totally predictable". For example, students might have to draw a map of their neighborhood and answer questions about the location of different places, such as the nearest bus stop, the nearest café, etc.

From the above, it can be observed that there are a lot of activities and different ways in which we can encourage students to better their communicative skills, as well as improving their communicative competence. These processes and practices are

contemplated in the light of the communicative language teaching approach, taking into account its ideals and expectation towards learners and their acquisition of a foreign language.

4.4 Content and Language Integrated Learning: CLIL

CLIL (Content and Language Integrated Learning), which has been defined as the integration of curricular content and learning, has created new prospects to the training of an L2 by linking it with the curriculum of each school. CLIL is mostly defined as a “dual-focused, learning and teaching approach in which a non-language subject is taught through a foreign language, with the dual focus being on acquiring subject knowledge and competences as well as skills and competences in the foreign language” (Ioannou Georgiu, 2012, p.495).

CLT is, according to the Council of Europe, “a notional-functional language-learning conceptualization” (Celce-Murcia, 2001, p.15). It seeks to build communicative competence, which can be said to encompass the three sub-categories of grammatical, discourse, sociocultural and strategic competences. CLT endorses implicit grammar teaching and inductive reasoning as key principles in language learning, thus promoting the more modern learner-centered classrooms, the teacher as a facilitator and meaning-construction among the learners in the language classroom. The communicative approach has been popular “since its theoretical origins in the seventies, and it gained curricular mandate in Norway in 1987” (Hellekjær 2005: 27). CLIL, with its integration of subject content with the English language, creates a learning-context where a certain topic or problem typically is subject to investigation, and therefore, produces real and meaningful communicative situations. Due to this fact, the CLIL-approach has been embellished by teachers of the CLT-classroom. Stated differently, CLIL is said to promote exactly the kinds of situations that initiate language acquisition; through natural language use – at the same time as providing increased motivation for learning the foreign language. One of the main considerations, crucial to the understanding the concept of CLIL, is that it is not simply or purely instruction given in a different language, but authentic facilitation of language acquisition by means of linguistic devices subtly inserted into the teaching of materials, with both in matter for evaluation.

Teaching with a CLIL format lesson in mind, can not only help students with an extra exposure to English but also cater for achieving the language goals, such as increasing

vocabulary or improving listening and speaking skills. Moreover, it helps bring diversity into the classroom and helps view the language from different cultural and educational angles (Ur, 2012). This approach triggers students' motivation to learn the language as they do not learn the language merely to know it, but to accomplish certain tasks and to get deeper knowledge of the subjects' content. Hence, "the language is used as a key to content" (Mehisto et al., 2008, p.11). Content-based instruction and consequently, CLIL, involve activities and tasks that are constructed so that they involve different skills at the same time, as it happens in the real world. Students can read academic texts and literary passages or watch a video clip and take notes, write summaries and discuss and comment on their writing. The language is viewed through the content, and grammar and vocabulary are considered as a part of discourse rather than "isolated fragments" (Richards and Rodgers, 2001, p.208). For that reason, it is the teacher the one who should carefully select the material and adequately select the language that will be relevant for a specific content matter.

In CLIL, comprehensible input is yielded by aiming the contents slightly higher than the level the learners are comfortable with, and integrating language-features with relevant content possibilities. Given the varying nature of each school subject within any program, this combination gives CLIL a flexibility which, according to applied linguist and CLIL-author Dieter Wolff, "should not be underestimated" (Marsh and Wolff, 2007, p.17). CLIL is in general believed to provide learners with better language input and subsequently better productivity and learning accomplishments.

According to Do Coyle et al., CLIL is more than a simple educational method, it is a new way of thinking about teaching and learning; an amalgamation that can be compared to the rise of other cross-disciplinary research fields such as environmental studies (Coyle 2010). David Marsh roughly defines CLIL as the simplest way of "bringing together excellence" from the fields of pedagogy, content teaching and immersion.

Even though there is a high inclusiveness by which CLIL popular definitions pride themselves, there is also a comparative lack of clarity in their concepts, which can complicate the continuous attempts at meticulous study (Cenoz, Genesee & Gorter 2013; Georgiou 2012). One of the reasons behind CLIL's popularity has also been its latitude and the resulting "transferability" across contexts (Coyle, Hood & Marsh 2010). In fact, one of the most noticeable "features" of CLIL is the wide variety of curricular models it encompasses. Grin (2005, cited in Coyle 2007) suggests the existence of as many as 216 types of CLIL programs differing from each other according to variables such as intensity, duration and age of learners when first enrolled into the program.

4.5 Design of CLIL didactic materials

There are challenges to CLIL such as the lack of CLIL teacher trainings, the laboriousness of the approach, and the pressure of national examinations felt by teachers are all serious difficulties, but probably the most pressing concern in CLIL teaching according to teachers and researchers alike, is the lack of appropriate teaching materials.

There have been several advocates who propose that teachers should become content developers for CLIL instead of using commercially generated coursebooks only. Teachers should revisit and focus on their own teaching concepts and pedagogical methods that direct learning and teaching through the production of CLIL materials. Both pre-service and in-service teacher courses are required to allocate further training opportunities for materials production based on a system that builds a powerful bridge between theory and practice in CLIL education.

As previously mentioned, CLIL demands training for teachers, as there is an apparent absence of marketed course books. Many teachers develop their own materials to deal with this issue. Moore and Lorenzo (2007) believe there may be three possibilities available for teachers when developing their own CLIL materials: to employ authentic sources without any modifications, to produce their own materials from scratch, or to adapt authentic materials according to their teaching aims.

In contrast to L1 mediating teaching, or L2 coursebook-based lessons, searching for and adapting existing materials at the same time as preparing new materials when appropriate, consumes a substantial amount of time and results in a greater workload for CLIL teachers. Teachers might also lack the “professional competences required in materials adaptation, supplementation and design” (Coonan 2007, p.628). However, there are some benefits for Teacher-developed CLIL materials for tertiary education since they can be excellent resources to meet the high demand for materials, as teachers can make them suitable for their learners and needs based on their context. There are some advantages for teacher-developed CLIL materials for tertiary education, as they can be excellent tools to meet the high demand for materials since teachers can make them suitable on the basis of their background for their learners and needs.

Furthermore, teachers who produce materials in collaboration between a specific subject and language benefit from a personal and professional development opportunity to reflect on their teaching practices and learning processes. In turn, the resources used integrate the students' involvement, motivation and cognitive development.

There is a need for studies on materials used in contents and language integrated learning, moreover, there is a shortage of research on the processes teachers employ to search, adapt and design materials for teaching CLIL. Coonan (2007, p.628) considers it a disadvantage that CLIL teachers must:

devote time searching for materials suitable for the learning objectives, to render the content accessible, to elaborate learning activities on these materials. Such work requires professional competences the teachers may not have, especially if such work has to be done in the L2.

Learning materials, teaching materials and materials tend to be conceptualized either as texts and tasks or as "anything that helps students learn" (Tomlinson, 2011, p.xiii). As a result, Tomlinson (2011, xiii–xiv) suggests that:

Materials can be in the form, for example, of a textbook, a workbook, a cassette, a CD-ROM, a video, a photocopied handout, a newspaper, a paragraph written on a whiteboard: anything which presents or informs about the language being learned.

The abilities to evaluate, adapt and produce materials are necessary for the modern teacher so he or she can ensure a match between the learners and the materials they use. Furthermore, materials development is also "a practical undertaking" involving "the production, evaluation and adaptation of language teaching materials, by teachers for their own classrooms and by materials writers for sale or distribution" (Tomlinson 2001, p. 66).

It is possible that authenticity is the most commonly discussed characteristic of CLIL materials, according to Lucietto it encompasses (2008, p.83) "texts which have been written for any purpose other than language teaching". The use of authentic and/or native speaker materials in CLIL teaching is recommended for it is believed to boost student motivation and increase teacher innovation.

One of the methods CLIL teachers turn to when looking for materials for their lessons is adaptation, a time-consuming enterprise although it ensures a better comprehension for

the learners than using unadapted authentic texts. Producing one's own CLIL materials from scratch is also a common undertaking among CLIL teachers. It enables teachers to "adjust the content and language of materials to fit the learners, curricula and cultural context the materials are meant for" (Moore & Lorenzo 2007, p.28–29). Apart from producing textbooks for CLIL teaching, providing suitable materials could mean setting up material banks and promoting cooperation and sharing among CLIL teachers

Some suggestions were put forward by researchers on how CLIL materials can be adapted or produced. Mehisto, Marsh and Frigols (2008, p.33) mention that texts can be adapted by "cutting information into manageable chunks and adding synonyms or a glossary" and by providing "visual or textual organizers". Meyer (2010) provides criteria for materials evaluation and selection based on second language acquisition research and Coyle's (2007) 4Cs-Framework but also suggests a complete framework for CLIL materials development. According to this framework, called the "CLIL-Pyramid", CLIL materials design should start with topic selection, then move on to the choice of media and then task-design. The design process should end with "CLIL-workout' – the review of key content and language elements". (Meyer 2010, p.23–24.)

The above suggestions and procedures such as the ones presented above may be useful advice for CLIL materials development. However, much still needs to be done in order to transform CLIL materials development into an educational practice based firmly on theory and empirical research.

In CLIL, there is a wide range of task types that teachers employ. To stimulate content and language production, students need a number of different tasks. Some tasks take more time to set up and develop, as well as more time to complete. One thing to remember is that maintaining a list of task kinds and ticking off those that have been used over an institution's term or year is beneficial. Some task types we can find in CLIL lessons of History are:

- Describe the picture and analyze the historical evidence it shows.
- Domino games
- Jigsaw text
- PowerPoint presentations
- Sequence events leading up to a change
- Word searches and web searches
- Matching sentences halves
- Multiple choice / odd one out

- Gap-filling activities
- Identification keys
- Find the mistakes or find the link between
- Circle, underline, tick the word sentence, or phrase, which is true.
- Classify information about a place in the past into categories
- Collect and organize information about a battle
- Compare and contrast historical maps or other sources
- Complete the timeline, table or drawing.
- Label or match sources and other images

After reviewing which tasks teachers can use in their lessons or can use as base to design their CLIL materials, they should ask themselves if these tasks motivate learners, involve interaction, need language support as well as develop thinking skills for the subject teachers teach.

Taking into account what we have discussed so far about the design of CLIL materials, it should be interesting to analyze a survey carried out with secondary CLIL learners from different countries (Bentley and Phillips, 2007). In their study, learners ages 13 to 16 from different schools implementing CLIL programs, were asked to tick a list of factors that help them learn school subjects in English. The results were the following: 38% of students reported pictures helped them in their learning, 19% of those students claimed diagrams and the use of computers were good resources, 18% claimed the same for word lists, 56% expressed teachers' explanations were useful, 49% said the same for the use of translations, and finally 36% of students claimed friends and their interaction with them was a positive factor in their learning of school subjects in English.

The results of the survey show, firstly, how significant it is that teachers explain their subject content effectively and secondly, if friends support each other in their classroom, it may be important to include experiential learning in CLIL classrooms. It is important to consider that scaffolding and encouragement to help students are key needs for learners in their first CLIL lessons. This can be in form of clearly presented step-by-step instructions or explanations, constructive feedback and use of language frames. It has been proven multiple times that learners have positive responses to meaningful contexts that personalize learning. It is also important to take into account the need of regular consolidation of new content and language.

4.6 Coyle's Frameworks for Developing CLIL Materials

There is no single model for CLIL. The general founding principle that in some way content and language learning are integrated is shared by different models of CLIL.

There are multiple authors that suggest different approaches to design CLIL materials and guide teachers in this arduous task. Coyle et al. (2010) is one of the more influential scholars, offering a structure for the creation of CLIL materials that further develops questions regarding cognitive difficulties followed by language support. They transition from building students' confidence in coping with the material and language they know in groups or more collaborative activities, to individual assignments and further language and content requirements. In this sense, practices shift from lower-order to higher-order thinking skills, and new language and content based on familiar language and content is scaffolded by materials. The following framework is based on this view:

Figure 1.1 CLIL lesson framework (Banegas 2010:8)

A Language Triptych is used to organize language activities so that materials should expose learners to:

- **language of learning**, that is, the learning of key words and phrases to access content,
- **language for learning** focusing on the language students will need to carry out classroom tasks such as explaining, and
- **language through learning** to make room for unpredictable language learning that may arise as the lesson unfolds. García (2013, p.51)

For example, if our aim is to plan a lesson about the Victorian Age, we can begin by utilizing familiar language such as simple present asking students: "Why do you think this period is called the 'Victorian Age'?". From the answers students provide, teachers can elicit familiar knowledge such as other queens and kings of the English monarchy (Queen Elizabeth, Queen Anne, King Henry, etc.). We may add them to a family tree by

means of more oral examples or videos taken from the Internet. We may add various structures such as possessive structures (example: "Queen Victoria was the daughter of Prince Edward."), the past simple, or completing sentences so that forms and functions are used. Students are then able to present and retell the data they have gathered in small groups, maybe in a poster in which they can evaluate what king/queen they think was most successful and why.

This CLIL "matrix" can be used for a more detailed lesson planning as they operate in three stages to be used with more specific content. The link between language and cognition (thinking and understanding) as seen by Coyle is complex, since according to him, effective learning involves cognitive challenge and feedback. Banegas (2010 pa. 10) claims that:

The CLIL matrix proposes 'quadrants. They move from building students' confidence, by resorting to the content and language they know through group or more interactive tasks to 'quadrants' in which learners deal with more individual tasks on the one hand, and further demands in terms of language and content on the other.

Much of the tasks include moving to a high linguistic domain from a low cognitive domain. Useful resources to provide scaffolding may be language boxes, mind frames, as well as teacher support. In addition, various intellectual, content and linguistic tools and technology may be used by teachers to support their teaching in order to promote learning.

This system can involve various exercises in two or more consecutive lessons to work the contents: from dances to storytelling, and can be presented with novels, original stories, realia, media support (CD, DVD, Interactive Whiteboard, etc.), songs or films from English-speaking authors orally or visually. Written and oral activities may take place, but it is important that those activities where a conversation is initiated are given special relevance.

Maintaining a conversation or a discussion in a foreign language can be a complex challenge at these points, so the main aim is to keep students in natural contact with the language, reflecting on the basic sense of what we are saying and ensuring that they have a general understanding that ensures a global understanding of the concepts worked throughout.

The suggested system includes teachers developing materials for tertiary education with the possibility of taking into account the point of view of a professional teacher (English teacher / Science teacher / History teacher / etc.), bearing in mind the principle of interrelation that features CLIL.

It is also helpful to think of Coyle's 4Cs of CLIL for planning lessons (Coyle, 1999) and how this can be applied, for example to history lessons.

- Content: What is the history of the topic? (example: the Industrial Revolution)
- Communication: What language will learners communicate during the lessons? (example: the language of reasoning: to communicate why Europeans were important for the success of the Industrial Revolution)
- Cognition: Which thinking skills are demanded of learners in the history lesson? (example: hypothesizing, thinking about what would have happened if the Industrial Revolution had not occurred)
- Culture (also referred as "Community" or "Citizenship"): Is there a cultural focus in the lesson? Example: learners can find out whether:
 - o The Industrial Revolution in England was successful because of the collaboration of other countries
 - o There is evidence of the Industrial Revolution nowadays in the products we use.
 - o The Industrial Revolution brought other positive side effects to the world.

It's important to highlight that "the perspectives of students from across the world can be used to make connections across a range of topics in the history curriculum" (Phillips, 2008, p.192).

CLIL claims that subject teachers are able to take advantage of language learning resources and opportunities and rely on the communicative approach. Learners will have the ability to improve their verbal and cognitive abilities by carrying out the proposed framework as they build up and describe their interactions, concepts, activities, etc.

In order to make them genuinely CLIL context-responsive, teachers need to create their own materials due to the lack of CLIL course books, training or a clear technique in tertiary education. Teachers can adopt principles published elsewhere and other models that are still to be applied and studied, but it is important that the content of the subject

is considered as the starting point of the material planning and development process, whatever form of model, it should be present all the time.

4.7 CLIL for teaching English History

The most important factor which CLIL focuses its attention on may be the learning of English and contents in a meaningful way. Although there are interesting studies about the success of CLIL teaching, little research has been done about teaching history with English as a medium of instruction in Argentina. As a result, there aren't plenty of studies about how studying historical content through an innovative approach may show better results than traditional methods in terms of learning history.

There are many considerations to take into account when planning a CLIL English History lesson or design materials for said lesson. One of those considerations is the activation of prior knowledge. Finding out what students already know about the history topic is a helpful method to start the lesson. Many of them may know facts about a topic in their first language but may encounter some difficulty explaining this knowledge in their second language. Because of that reason, it is common that when brainstorming ideas about a new topic, learners use some of the L1 or translate.

The wait time is another important factor to address. It relates to the time teachers wait between asking questions and being answered by learners. When History as a subject is taught in a non-native language, learners need a longer wait-time than usual in order to process the recently discovered concepts in a new language. This is especially true at the start of new CLIL lessons or implementation of new CLIL materials in the classroom. The aim is that all students are encouraged to take part in classroom interaction.

Students usually need considerable support to develop their thinking skills in a non-native language. This cognitive challenge means they need to communicate not only the everyday functional language practiced in many English classes, but they also need to communicate the cognitive, academic language of school subjects. In turn, cognitive challenging CLIL materials are used by learners from the beginning of their lessons.

Another significant factor is that the input, that is, the material being provided in the CLIL class, must be prepared by teachers. Also defined by the Longman Dictionary of

Language Teaching and Applied Linguistics (1992, p.261) as “language which a learner hears or receives and from which he or she can learn.”. Teachers need to decide if this input will be delivered orally, in writing, electronically, on paper, etc. They also need to consider if this input will be for whole-class work, group or pair work, moreover, will it include the use of source materials? The students’ output should also be planned, that is, how learners are going to produce and communicate the content and language of the lesson. It may be communicated orally, in writing or by using practical skills.

The use of collaborative talks is also key to involve learners in producing significant history-specific vocabulary and structures in meaningful pair or group work activities. These tasks may be at word level, such as pairs of students classifying vocabulary into different columns in a table, or at sentence level, for example, pairs can ask and answer questions about life 200 years ago. Moreover, groups can explain how they plan to research life in Britain in the 19th century and present the information they have found. They can do this digitally or face-to-face. Some of the most common digital resources are PowerPoint Presentations, Prezi Presentations, or even YouTube videos. Activities should support processing of new history content and language.

Scaffolding, that is the content and language support strategies which are appropriate but temporary, are very important. Also defined by the Longman Dictionary of Language Teaching and Applied Linguistics (1992, p.466) as:

The support provided to learners to enable them to perform tasks which are beyond their capacity. Initially in language learning, learners may be unable to produce certain structures within a single utterance, but may build them through interaction with another speaker.

Providing it effectively in lessons is a challenge to all CLIL teachers since learners vary in the amount of support they need and, in the length, and time the support is needed. Students might need more supports and for longer in one topic than in another.

Another significant factor to take into account when planning a CLIL English History lesson or design materials for said lesson is the development of thinking skills. Teachers need to ask questions which encourage lower order thinking skills, that is according to Bloom’s Taxonomy (Bloom, 1956, p.25), those skills include, “remembering, understanding, and applying” or the “what, when, where and which questions”. Nonetheless, they will need to ask questions that require higher order thinking skills, which include why and how questions are posed and also require more nuanced

vocabulary to be used. At an early stage of learning about history in CLIL contexts, students often are expected to answer higher order thinking questions. To exemplify, a 10-year-old can be asked “The price of books dropped after the invention of the printing press, why do you think this happened?”.

4.8 CLIL challenges for History teachers

Designing and implementing CLIL is not an easy task as we have seen, there are many challenges that History teachers encounter and need to overcome when using this methodology. For instance, history teachers should feel sure about their English language level, particularly if they have not used English for a while. This is because in History, teachers need to be able to use appropriate classroom language to present arguments, to question, paraphrase, encourage, clarify and manage their classes. Moreover, students ought to be able to present and discuss historical information and sources in a clear and accurate manner.

Language teachers may decide to teach their lessons in CLIL or may be asked to. For that reason, they ought to be feel confident about their own subject knowledge and skills since they are going to be teaching it. They need to know how to explain historical evidence, analyze sources, and select relevant information and materials for learners of different ages in meaningful and creative ways that will deepen learner’s understanding and improve their English and History knowledge. Furthermore, language teachers need to widen their knowledge of vocabulary related to specific history topics and pronunciation, be prepared to answer questions about history with answers that may be unfamiliar to the learners.

On part of the students, most of them need considerable support in their first CLIL lessons. The majority of teachers do not know how long learners will take to do tasks, complete worksheets or understand instructions and explanations until they have used materials for the first time. Learners are all different, some need more support than others in order to understand subject concepts. Moreover, other students might need support to communicate ideas about those subject concepts.

Moving between L1 and the target language, either mid-sentence or between sentences is quite common for learners in CLIL. This is known as code switching and it can be also defined as:

A change by a speaker (or writer) from one language or language variety to another one. Code switching can take place in a conversation when one speaker uses one language and the other speaker answers in a different language. A person may start speaking one language and then change to another one in the middle of their speech, or sometimes even in the middle of a sentence. (Longman Dictionary of Language Teaching and Applied Linguistics, 1992, p.81)

The use of L1 and the target language happens when clarifying teachers' instructions, developing ideas for curricular content, off-task social comments, encouraging peers, and group negotiations among others. Unless teachers find themselves in a situation where using the L1 could benefit or reassure learners, it is important that they avoid using regularly in class. This means teachers should be able to justify their use of L1.

Another challenge teachers may face is CLIL assessment, which is defined by the Longman Dictionary of Language Teaching and Applied Linguistics (1992, p.35) as

a systematic approach to collecting information and making inferences about the ability of a student or the quality or success of a teaching course on the basis of various sources of evidence. Assessment may be done by test, interview, questionnaire, observation, etc.

Teachers are unsure whether to assess content, language or both. A variety of places, institutions and teachers assess in different ways. The key issue is that in CLIL subjects there is formative as well as summative evaluation and the continuity in how learners in each school are evaluated across subjects. To clarify, Black & William, (2009, p.7) claim:

Practice in a classroom is formative to the extent that evidence about student achievement is elicited, interpreted, and used by teachers, learners, or their peers, to make decisions about the next steps in instruction that are likely to be better, or better founded, than the decisions they would have taken in the absence of the evidence that was elicited.

On the other hand, summative assessments "are used to evaluate student learning, skill acquisition, and academic achievement at the conclusion of a defined instructional period - typically at the end of a project, unit, course, semester, program, or school year" (Concepts., 2013, p.1). For students, parents and teachers alike, what learners are graded on and how they are evaluated is basic knowledge. Performance evaluation is one successful type of formative evaluation which:

involves learners in demonstrating their knowledge of content and language. For example, they could explain why they chose particular diagrams of different pyramids and analyze the floor plans or evaluate the plans and explain why they show progress in the development of design. (Tomlinson, 2001, p.56):

The assessment and observation of the learners' performance is done by teachers using specific criteria. Performance assessment can involve individuals, pairs or groups of learners. Since CLIL encourages task-based learning, it is appropriate that learners have opportunities to be tested by demonstrating both individually and collaboratively what they can do. This type of assessment can also be used to evaluate the development of communicative and cognitive skills, as well as attitude towards learning. Teachers can look for evidence of learners' ability to describe one of the pyramid's floor plans in detail (communication), reflect on their choice of sources (cognitive skills); and plan the gathering of data collaboratively (attitude).

4.9 Solutions for teachers to overcome the challenges of CLIL

Solutions for history teachers:

- To use a grammar reference book in order to practice producing questions which involve higher order thinking skill such as expressing cause and effect.
For example:
 - In the 18th century, what was the result of the Indian Removal Act.
 - What caused the Industrial Revolution?
 - Agriculture suffered a crisis, what led to this situation?

- To use an online dictionary with an audio track to hear the pronunciation of history vocabulary.

- To make sure learners know the functional language needed to talk about their subjects.

Solutions for language teachers:

- To use online resources or subject-related books in English or the L1, read about history and the key concepts learners will need to understand and communicate.

- To practice their delivery of history materials, prepare questions which demand lower and higher order thinking skills and predict questions learners may ask about the topics exposed.
- To place emphasis on the subject-specific vocabulary learners need and present new words in topic-related word banks and place them in order of hierarchy. For example: 12th century trades: master craftsmen, journeymen, apprentices, and so on.

Language teachers and history teachers alike, can also plan curricular topics together so that both benefit from each other's area of expertise.

4.10 Considerations for teachers when planning for CLIL

There is a wide range of factors subjects and language teachers alike need to take into considerations when planning a CLIL lesson or designing CLIL materials. One of the most crucial ones is what content learners will revisit and what content will be new to them. They need to be exposed to subject-specific language more than once, for that reason, revisiting a new concept is necessary. To revisit certain concepts, teachers should present learners with different tasks that demand several language skills but that are aimed at communication of the same concepts. Moreover, teachers should also note any anticipated difficulties learners may have with content and language learning while planning.

Another factor teachers should take into account is the learning outcomes of each lesson. What learners will know and understand about history, what they will be able to do at the end of the class, what abilities they will master and what attitudes they will build about teamwork are all important factors that should be taken into account for the learning outcomes and goals. Learning outcomes are learner-centered as they focus on what the learners can achieve rather than on what the teacher is teaching.

Because CLIL encourages collaborative learning, there are some pair work or group work activities which ought to be planned beforehand for learners to communicate the language of the subject topic. This is no easy task, even more, if we want to teach history if the learners' L1 is non-European. Rather than leave communicative activities to the end of the class, teachers should integrate them into during the lesson. These can be short (for example: tell learners they have 5 minutes to agree with a classmate where to

mark six events about the reign of Queen Victoria) or long (for example: tell learners they have 15 minutes to study the most important facts of the 18th century and to explain three main sources why these took place).

Continuing with the multiple factors teachers should consider when planning for CLIL, is the kind of tasks learners will do during the lesson and as follow-ups. It is important to plan a range of tasks which require different challenges, such as less demanding tasks which involve matching sentences halves, making trade routes on old maps, or marking events in timelines. More demanding tasks include explaining causes and effects, evaluating evidence, providing evidence of change from a text and giving reasons why something happened the way it did.

Teachers need to find or create materials and then evaluate them to make sure the content and language are suitable for the stage the learners are at in all teaching. Most subject materials in CLIL are in need of adaptation on account of their language complexity often encountered in instructions, written work or in the activities themselves. Moreover, this can also be an issue when teachers recommend history websites for learners to access. Web links should be checked to ensure the language is comprehensible before asking learners to access the information.

The development of both thinking and learning skills also needs to be planned beforehand. Teachers should consider if learners move from lower to higher thinking skills during the lesson. Teachers need to plan and sometimes practice types of questions they will ask to develop both types of thinking. For example, a lower order thinking questions for the purpose of reviewing learning, could be “When was the Treaty of Paris signed and who signed it?”. In turn, a higher order thinking questions to develop hypothesizing skills could be “How could the treaty have helped the countries which didn't sign it?”.

CLIL promotes links with other subjects in the curriculum so teachers should plan to include references to learning similar content in other subjects. For example, if students are studying the topic of 16th century kings and queens, they can look at an old map and then make links to contemporary maps to notice changes in the interpretations of maps, in names of countries and ports (geography).

All teachers may need to plan how to support the language input and output during CLIL lessons. Sometimes support for input and output can be the same. It is helpful to think of support at word, sentence and text levels. In history, tasks usually include all three.

For example: “steam-powered” (word-level support), “the steam train was invented by...” (sentence-level support).

It is important to link the assessment of learning, that is the formative assessment, to the attainment of learning outcomes for the lessons. Assessment criteria can be transparent. For example, a learning outcome could be “Most learners should know that the Age of Enlightenment happened during the 18th century” or “Most learners should explain some events and changes during the Tudor times using source materials”. However, an assessment could be “Most learners can summarize aspects of 18th-century life”.

Ongoing records of continuous, formative assessment should be done through observation of learning experiences in the classroom. The recording of information about each learner during each lesson is not necessary. However, over a period of several weeks, evidence of learners’ progress as they work towards achieving the learning outcomes needs to be recorded.

5. METHODOLOGY OF THE PROJECT

5.1 Approach selected for the design of the materials.

The design of the CLIL materials in this paper were based on Coyle's Frameworks for Developing CLIL Materials (2010). The steps of this approach move from building the trust of students by resorting to the content and language they understand through community or more interactive tasks to 'quadrants' in which, on the one hand, learners deal with more individual tasks and, on the other hand, more language and content requirements.

This "matrix" needs also to cater to a careful balance in terms of language and content learning. Similar to the taxonomy shown in Figure 1, materials should be arranged by teachers in the following order: familiar language, familiar content, new content and new language.

As explained before in the theoretical framework, to organise language activities better, Coyle et al. (2010) develops a Language Triptych. Materials should introduce learners to the language of learning, i.e., learning key terms and phrases to access information, language for learning that focuses on language learners may need to conduct tasks in the classroom, such as discussion, and language through learning to make room for unpredictable language learning that can occur as the lesson unfolds. If the lesson starts with a text, teachers need to look at its complexity, that is, its linguistic and cognitive challenge, to make sure that materials move from familiar language and content to new content and language. They can manage such a sequence by exploring bullet-point texts, tables and diagrams and more visuals. Teachers can also adapt texts through synonyms, cognates, and simplification of language and content load per sentence.

As discussed previously, CLIL takes a learner-centered approach, which belongs to the active learning approaches since teachers serve as facilitators and learners are put to all study effort and thought. Working in pairs and groups decreases the distress of failure for learners and, on the other hand, develops inspiration and collaborative practice helps to achieve results in language, material and learning. Several pieces of research have demonstrated active learning success, including that of Rotgans and Schmidt (2011), who studied how situational interest evolved over time and how it was connected to academic achievement in an active learning classroom.

According to the framework defined, the CLIL materials designed in this paper aim to respond to concerns about cognitive growth, along with the desired balance linking the content and language components of the CLIL classroom. This is also because it organizes sources and practices in relation to teacher-developed content, so that lessons become an enjoyable and cohesive learning proposition.

5.2 Target group

For the aim of this paper, these CLIL materials were designed for their implementation in an English History course at a tertiary instruction called “New Start” in Paraná, Entre Ríos, Argentina. In this group there are twenty students, their ages ranging from 18 to 22 years old. They are all in their first year of their English Teaching or English Translation courses. To obtain their degree, students must advance throughout their courses passing all the subjects in their curriculum, one of them being English History. All students share Spanish as their mother tongue, while some of them have a good level of English, others struggle understanding the language. This may be because primary as well as secondary schools in Paraná, either public or private, have a different range level of English proficiency being taught. There are schools in which students are proficient in English and are even given the chance to participate in Cambridge ESOL examinations at the end of their secondary education. However, there are other schools in which students end their secondary education with little to no knowledge of the English language.

For the reasons mentioned above, many drop out of their subjects because they don't have the necessary knowledge to understand English either written or spoken, especially if the language used is academic or specific to the subject.

Students are used to having two classes a week for a period of one hour each. This is an annual subject and because of the coronavirus lockdown, right now they are having lessons via Zoom.

As explained previously in the justification and objectives' section of this paper, it is hoped that by designing and implementing CLIL materials in the English History subjects, students will be able to become more motivated and better users of the English language, apart from gaining the required knowledge of the subject.

These students are expected to have or reach a B2-level of English according to the Common European Framework of Reference (CEFR). As specified by this framework, with a B2 level, students:

- CAN follow or give a talk on a familiar topic or keep up a conversation on a fairly wide range of topics.
- CAN scan texts for relevant information, and understand detailed instructions or advice.
- CAN make notes while someone is talking or write a letter including non-standard requests.
- CAN keep up a conversation on a fairly wide range of topics, such as personal and professional experiences, events currently in the news.
- CAN understand detailed information, for example, a wide range of culinary terms on a restaurant menu, and terms and abbreviations in accommodation advertisements.
- CAN write to a hotel to ask about the availability of services, for example, facilities for the disabled or the provision of a special diet.
- CAN give a clear presentation on a familiar topic, and answer predictable or factual questions.
- CAN scan tests for relevant information and grasp main point of text.
- CAN make simple notes that will be of reasonable use for essay or revision purposes.

It is expected that these abilities can be reached at the end of the year by students who have struggled in their production and understanding of the language. This may also be achieved by the design and implementation of CLIL materials along with the materials already used (books, academic tests, PowerPoint presentations, flashcards, coursebooks, etc.) to improve their content knowledge of the English History subject.

5.3 Structure, typology and creative process of the materials

As explained, the approach used for the design of the CLIL materials will be based on Coyle's framework. Taking that into consideration, the structure of said materials will be as follows: The activities will change from building the confidence of students with the content and language they know in groups or more collaborative tasks, to individual tasks and further language and content requirements.

The CLIL materials will also take a communicative approach, since the use of communicative tasks is an excellent tool to develop the communicative competence as it makes our students reflect on, appreciate, and implement communicative behaviors not only within the context of a foreign language classroom, but also in the real world where sometimes they find it useless.

The designed materials not only needed to fit the CLIL approach, but it also needed to be authentic, motivational and enjoyable for students. However, these characteristics can only take place if there is an actual engagement of the students with the materials. Shernoff (2013, p.12) defines student engagement as “the heightened simultaneous experience of concentration, interest, and enjoyment in the task at hand”. Students, who experience few positive emotions and higher levels of negative emotions, have lower engagement with school and learning. For that reason, it is key that students feel motivated towards their learning, as it is part of what it is to be a self-regulated learner. Students’ beliefs about whether or not they can be successful in school, may be considered a motivational construct in their use of the CLIL materials. In order to engage students, students need to experience positive emotional experiences. These experiences build a positive classroom climate, which is the basis of student-teacher relationships and interactions.

Taking what was said above into consideration, it is also important to bear in mind that the CLIL materials had to take into account self-regulated learning. This has to do with how students manage their motivation, behavior and learning in the institution. When doing activities or tasks in class, students set goals then monitor and regulate their learning to reach those goals. This self-regulation, if properly considered by the materials designed, can be powerful towards allowing students to plan, persist and think about their actions. In challenging situations, students who have been significantly motivated by well-designed CLIL materials, employ new learning strategies that work to adapt when those aren’t working in a specific task.

In my personal experience in the classroom with my students, the use of different materials apart from textbooks was beneficial for their motivation and learning process in the subject. Apart from considering what was discussed about the different elements to be considered when designing this CLIL material, my creative process during the design of the activities was also based on providing students with different types of activities from each topic, something which is supported by the CLIL methodology. That meant designing English activities, reading, writing and communicative tasks.

The use and adaptation of authentic materials was also considered to be useful. By relying on multiple sources, these types of materials bring learners into direct contact with a reality level of English. Any texts written by native English speakers for native English speakers can become good resources for activities such as the ones mentioned earlier.

It may be said that the CLIL materials were designed following these main stages:

- Selection of topic
- Research of authentic material
- Design of activities stemming from the authentic materials

I will now briefly discuss each stage to make my creative process clearer. The first stage, selection of topic, was done taking into account the most important topics given during the year in the curriculum of the English History subject. There will be three materials designed based on three topics: The Tudors, The Victorian Age and Elizabeth I. These topics were chosen because they are fundamental moments of English History and are predominant in the subject curriculum. Apart from that, I believed they were good resources in terms of vocabulary and grammar, considering what students usually have to study in their English Language subject in their first year at the institution.

The authentic material can be found mainly in textbooks and the Internet. There are infinite ways in which these materials can be found and adapted in order to fit the objectives of the designed CLIL materials for particular tasks. The actual design or what students “see” at first glance is also very important. It is not the same to see a black and white activity with an old photograph which may be blurry or even be unrelated to the topic at hand than to see a modern design with colorful pictures. These may even include cartoons or comics which cater to visual learners and also motivate students to be engaged with the material.

After having chosen one particular material, a lot of activities can stem from it (as the ones discussed throughout this paper). You can find these available in the Appendix section of this paper. Some considerations that needed to be made before choosing the authentic source, were if the content was directly relevant to the student’s needs, if students will feel comfortable enough with the linguistic level required from them and if the information was relevant to the topic students needed to study. This also had to do with the learning objectives of the materials, which needed to be taken into consideration

before actually designing the CLIL materials that were going to be used in class. These objectives are discussed in the following section of this paper.

5.5 General learning objectives of the materials

First of all, when developing CLIL resources, teaching aims or goals and learning outcomes for both language and content should be considered. We experience information through teaching goals and skills teachers plan to teach. Objectives are defined as short, explicit statements that define the instruction's desired learning outcomes; i.e., students should display specific skills, values, and attitudes that represent the wider objectives.

Learning outcomes, on the other hand, identify what the learner will know and be able to do by the end of a lesson. Bentley (2009) proposes learning outcomes, should be measurable and achievable at the same time, to help the teachers as well as learners to have a clear idea of what goals are to be achieved. Learning results, on the other hand, describe what the learner will know and be able to do at the end of a class. In order to enable teachers and learners to have a better understanding of what expectations are to be accomplished, Bentley (2009) suggests learning outcomes that should be observable and realistic at the same time.

Coyle (2005) believes that it is important to represent in CLIL lessons that the language is driven by the substance of the subject. In addition, two major variables should be remembered as follows: expectations for teaching and results for learning. Broadly speaking, as a consequence of a learning experience or outcome, all educational purposes can be described in one of two ways - what the instructor is intended to do - a teaching aim and what the student is intended to have learned or will be able to do.

There are different learning objectives which these materials aim to achieve, and for this purpose, there were specific areas in which to focus:

- Making progress visible: Progress can be achieved in cautious planning. In general, language, content and learning skills have to be broken down into smaller units and long term and short term planned outcomes. The students as the key element must be introduced to the set goals. It is believed that students first need to know and understand the goal in order to achieve it. Above all only

stimulating, inspiring and thought-provoking CLIL material and tasks will lead the way to an achievable learning outcome. Above all only stimulating, inspiring and thought-provoking CLIL material and tasks will lead the way to an achievable learning outcome

- Promoting academic language proficiency: No one can expect learners to acquire whole academic language in one go. It also has to be broken down and introduced systematically. Materials should, therefore, reflect step-by-step advancement leading to short and long-term learning outcomes. The materials designed are expected to provide students with logical and systematic academic language introduction. This can be achieved by drawing students' attention to various language forms such as specific vocabulary, connectors, words with different meanings, and functions are in preference. This can be achieved by drawing students' attention to various language forms such as specific vocabulary, connectors, words with different meanings, and functions are in preference.

- Encouragement of learner's autonomy and learning skills: Learner autonomy is not an inherited skill but rather it is a skill requiring lots of directed practice. Being an autonomous learner means the ability to direct one's own learning. It is a long-term process supported by students' intrinsic motivation and teacher leadership. Well-designed materials should above all indicate the path an autonomous learner needs to take in problem-solving tasks. Consequently, materials should help the learner to gather and improve the skills found necessary to deal with assignments. It might include tips on how to complete a given assignment. Consequently, materials should help the learner to gather and improve the skills found necessary to deal with assignments. It might include tips on how to complete a given assignment.

- Authenticity: It deals mainly with a target language which needs to be incorporated into materials in such a way it not only provides authentic language but also urges learners to use it. The tasks should be oriented predominantly on everyday language, information from media and suggested Internet research to develop the topic. Personalization seems to be another tool for authentic materials.

- Fostering critical thinking: CLIL materials are not based on straightforward repetition of the learnt facts or recollection of those facts. In contrast, exercises are oriented to a higher order of thinking- creation, evaluation, analysis, application and understanding

- Significant learning is also part of the standards established for the development of a learning content. It is the general truth that fascinating and important knowledge appears to be memorized because it could be considered as necessary information for future life growth and application. Thus, the personal interests of learners, group life and life should be expressed in CLIL materials.

Apart from focusing on the above general criteria for the objectives of designing appropriate materials, useful CLIL resources provide knowledge of what is to be learned - the aims and how to teach it - materials, facilities, and activities.

The following general objectives of the designed CLIL materials take into account the 4Cs:

Content:

- The Tudor, Elizabethan and Victorian Age.

Cognition:

- To have a general idea of what the Victorian, Elizabethan and Tudor period entailed.
- To identify and find information about the most important kings and queens from the periods mentioned.
- To learn what each monarch achieved during their reign.
- To classify monarchs into their most important achievements
- To evaluate different opinions about the different ages described.
- To give oral presentations about the topics learned.
- To exchange information and opinions with classmates by pair and group work.
- To make predictions before having all the information about a certain topic.
- To analyze pictures and do gap-filling exercises.

Communication:

Language of learning:

- Present and past tenses.
- Comparatives and superlatives.
- Prepositions, adjectives, verbs, adverbs and nouns.
- Fundamental vocabulary

Language for learning:

- Strategies for reading and comprehension a text.
- Strategies to enhance conversation in the classroom by exchanging thoughts and results.
- Strategies for oral presentations.

Language through learning:

- Other vocabulary which students may be unfamiliar with.

Culture:

- To understand the culture of each period and the changing times throughout English History.

6. RESULTS AND DISCUSSION

6.1 Context

Whereas teacher beliefs are individual (and internal) and linked to a specific individual, external variables will also be taken into account when designing CLIL materials. In this section I will be discussing the external variables in which these materials were implemented and which were taken into account for the actual design and choices made in them.

These materials were designed using Microsoft Word to be implemented at New Start, a private institution in the city of Paraná (Entre Ríos, Argentina), as a response to certain specific needs in the fields of English and American History and English Language. The aim of this institution was to develop strong activities with an effective linguistic approach and methodology in order to increase and maintain an upright position in the region in the field of English language learning.

The participants were 20 students, ranging in age from 18 to 22. They are all part of their English Teaching or English Translation courses in their first year. Students must advance throughout their courses to get their degree by passing all the subjects in their curriculum, one of which is English History.

All students share the Spanish mother tongue, some of them have a good level of English, while others struggle to understand the language. This may be because a different level of English proficiency is taught in both primary and secondary schools in Paraná, either public or private. There are schools in which students are proficient in English and are even given the opportunity at the end of their secondary education to participate in the Cambridge ESOL exams. There are, however, other schools in which students are with little to no knowledge of the English language at the end of their secondary education. Many drop out of their subjects for the reasons listed above, because they do not have the required knowledge to understand either written or spoken English, especially if the language used is academic or unique to the subject.

For a time of one hour each, learners are used to attending two classes a week. This is an annual topic and they are having lessons via Zoom right now because of the coronavirus lockdown. This means students have started their first year of their English

Teaching or Translation courses in March of 2020 and are in a state of isolation and restricted access instituted by the security measures of COVID-19. However, during these challenging times, most students have WIFI available, are able to share their screen and are encouraged to actively participate during class, which demands them to have their microphones and video cameras active at all times. Although going from having face-to-face classes in the institute to having all classes online was not easy either on teachers or students, however, they raised to the challenge and demonstrated a good performance and understanding of the subject during the lessons.

This transition was also made easy since students have a Virtual Campus where they can see and handle assignments or homework, along with announcements from the teacher and the materials of the curriculum. The main material learners use to study the contents of the subject is the book "An Illustrated History of Britain" by David McDowall (1989), complemented by the book "An Illustrated History of the USA" by Denis Brynley O'Callaghan (1990). Most of the time they are assigned chapters to read before class and then in class, we do a summary of what they have read, discuss their opinion of some of the topics and then they learn more information about the topics through a PowerPoint Presentation shared via Zoom. After discussing what they have read, broaden their knowledge of the topics and then shared opinions about them, they do a series of activities, either individually or in groups (this can be done by using the "breakout rooms" option in Zoom). This is the format of most of our classes.

This group of students are young adults learning to be self-directed in their learning, with supplies of experience that can serve as resources as they learn. Throughout the lessons we had from the beginning of the year, they showed to be practical, problem-solving-oriented learners. They do not expect the subject of English History to be immediately applicable to their lives, but they often make connection between English culture and history with their own. Some of these students also expect to know why something needs to be learned, as a result it is important to set the objectives and give clear instructions in each task and activity students are asked to do.

As discussed earlier in the rationale and goals section of this paper, it is hoped that students would be able to become more inspired and better users of the English language, apart from acquiring the necessary knowledge of the subject, by designing and implementing CLIL materials in the English History subject.

From a chronological point of view, the topics are not far from each other, but rather are taught one after the other. Most of the materials share characteristics or elements in

common. Regarding grammar, for example, most of the materials cover the topic of comparatives and superlatives, either in a receptive or productive form. This is because it is a topic these students struggle with at the beginning of their courses and which is fundamental in order to make comparisons between different history periods, monarchs, or even between English culture and their own. Another characteristic most of these materials have in common is the practice of giving and asking for opinions, along with making predictions or inferences. This is because this skill is paramount in the rest of the subjects from the curriculum students are currently undertaking and for the ones in the future. This communicative skill also involves a meaningful social exchange with feedback that students will then turn to learning and understanding of new words and structures.

Apart from the two elements mentioned before, there are a lot of other characteristics shared between the three materials, most of which relate to the structure students learn and practice, the key competences and language skills. The materials focus on some of the main needs of the students of this institution taking into account their linguistic and communicative abilities. This does not mean that other topics, structures or skills are to be disregarded, since they can be learned or practice through the resources implemented before or after using these materials. The contents of the materials were chosen according to the context previously discussed and the curriculum of the English History subject.

6.2 Materials' general information

As stated previously, all the materials are organized for the purpose of being implemented in English History classes at an undergraduate course of adult language students with a B2-level of English proficiency according to the Common European Framework of English. In this group there are twenty students, their ages ranging from 18 to 22 years old, who will use the materials labeled as follows:

- A. The Tudors
- B. Elizabeth I
- C. The Victorian Age

The activities found in these materials were designed to be given in a paper format for students to work, but they can also look at them from their respective electronic devices. Also, some teachers may opt to show the activities through a projector in the classroom

or a PowerPoint Presentation. As it can be noticed, there are a lot of possible ways in which the materials can be presented depending on the context of each teacher and his/her classroom.

Regarding the learning objectives of the materials, which were mentioned and explained in the methodology of this paper, the design of these materials achieved to aim the following:

- Making progress visible
- Promoting academic language proficiency
- Encouragement of learner's autonomy and learning skills
- Authenticity
- Fostering critical thinking

Along with these objectives, other aims taking into account the 4Cs: Contents, Cognition, Communication and Culture. These were mentioned more extensively on page 40 of this paper, and will be mentioned again later in relevance to the analysis of each of the three materials designed.

At first, these materials were meant to be implemented in paper format (each student would have had their own copy), but because of the recent COVID pandemic, the material was implemented in an online classroom format, using a PowerPoint Presentation shown through Zoom. Of course, these materials weren't implemented in a single class, but rather in three separate classes as they discuss three different set of topics. Each class lasted from 40 minutes to an hour, taking into account that in some of them, students had to use other resources apart from the ones designed. These resources ranged from their history books to videos and online quizzes, which can be easily found in the Internet and implemented as a complement to the designed materials.

The font I chose to design these materials was Montserrat Regular and for the main title Patrick Hand. This is because students are used to seeing fonts like Arial, Times New Roman or Comic Sans in almost all materials, which can become tiring or boring to them. I believe that by choosing another font which is clear yet new to them, they may be more receptive and encouraged towards the material and activities. When we make small changes in what students encounter in an everyday basis, like the fonts we use when designing a material, we may see positive benefits in our lessons.

It is worth mentioning that students should have some previous knowledge about the topics of the designed materials, as they are meant to summarize or discuss some specific parts of history. On their own, the knowledge learned from these materials would not be sufficient to pass the subject of English History (at least in my case) and would not allow students to accomplish an overall sense of what the English History topics entails. For that reason, and as I mentioned previously, these materials should be used as complements and summaries for the topics previously discussed in class.

Most of the materials follow a similar pattern, as they focus mainly on CLIL following a Communication Approach. Reading and speaking are highly prominent in each topic along with specific subject-related vocabulary. As mentioned previously, Meyer (2010) provides criteria for materials evaluation and selection based on second language acquisition research and Coyle's (2007) 4Cs-Framework but also suggests a complete framework for CLIL materials development. According to this framework, called the "CLIL-Pyramid", CLIL materials design should start with topic selection, then move on to the choice of media and then task-design. The design process should end with "*CLIL-workout' – the review of key content and language elements*". (Meyer 2010, p.23–24.) This is the framework in which these materials were designed, trying to follow a similar arrangement in the type of activities, skills, objectives, and more.

In the following sections, the materials will be discussed in a chronological order, firstly mentioning why the topic chosen for each one is fundamental for students' learning in the subject curriculum, then I will briefly mention a summary of the content of the materials, and finally I will explain using a table format other factors such as the objectives, content, key competences, student interpersonal communication learning, tasks and activities, evaluation, etc.

To present the materials in a clear manner, I mentioned some of the above characteristics are presented in a table format. For that reason, I will briefly mention and explain these.

Starting with the learning outcomes of each material, the objectives, topic content and key competences are discussed. The first deals with the goals which students are expected to achieve in that material, the second has to do with the specific topic that is discussed in English in that material, and the third relates to the unique essential skills/competences to be applied: verbal, quantitative, psychological, digital, educational, learning to read, autonomy, etc.

Following the learning outcomes, the elements composing the student interpersonal communication learning are discussed. Those refer to the communication skills we use every day as we connect and engage with other individuals, both personally and in groups. Interpersonal skills have a broad range of abilities, but especially communication skills such as listening and communicating effectively. The elements within this part of the table are: Vocabulary (the primary vocabulary included in the material the student should learn and revise), Structures (grammar and discourse structures present in the material which comply with the English class revision) and Language skills (communicate language skills to be practiced throughout the material, either being receptive or productive).

Finally, the organization of tasks and activities is discussed, taking into account two elements: the tasks and activities themselves, along with the instructions/considerations for teachers. At first, the table briefly explains the activities the student will complete throughout the material either at the beginning or culmination of what he/she has learned during the material. Then, the table explains what considerations teachers should bear in mind when using these activities: how long will an activity take, if students can do it either individually or in pairs, and possible benefits or problems that could be encountered in each of them.

6.3 The Tudors

As mentioned before, the first material to be discussed is “The Tudors” (Appendix 1). It consists of five activities about the Tudor Age and its kings and queens, namely, Henry VII, Henry VIII, Mary I and Elizabeth I.

This material mainly focuses on teaching students about the Tudor period and the Tudor kings and queens, giving a summary of each one and contemplating some of the main events from those times.

Although the Tudors are from more than 400 years ago, today it is fundamental and interesting for students to study and know about. It was not a flawless monarchy, and violence, religious bigotry, and controversy filled their reign. In England, however, the Tudors officially ended the Middle Ages. In the nation that England is nowadays, they have played a major part. The Tudor legacy transformed England from a tiny, mysterious

island to one of the biggest powers in Europe. They have placed their country on the radar of the nations, where it has remained since.

What sometimes happens at History lessons with History teachers is that they place too much emphasis or only focus on the two Tudor monarchs: Henry VIII and Elizabeth I. However, in my experience their reigns lead us to believe that Henry and Elizabeth are not the ideal, awesome leaders that everyone thinks. On the other hand, Henry VII, Mary, and Edward are more critical than we know. This is why the activities from the material aim to teach every one of the monarchs, leaving out any bias about popularity.

Now after talking a little bit about the importance of the topic of this material in particular, I will summarize the activities and tasks of the material overall. The material starts by asking students to look at visual aids of some of the events from the Tudor period, this will help stimulate their interest and allow the teacher to assess what they already know about the topic. Moreover, it will also challenge students to rethink what they already know about the topic and test their own thinking and inferring skills. The same could be said with the second activity, where students have to discuss among themselves about the main problems of the Tudor Age and look back on what information they already know about the topic. Later on, in the third activity students read a little summary about each Tudor monarch and after, they need to organize what facts belong to each monarch. This will help students revisit the information they have already read and also aid them in their search to find the most important facts or pieces of information about each monarch. In the fourth activity students look back on the predictions they made in the second activity, aiming to see if they were wrong or right about what they talked about with their peers. This type of activity is engaging for them since it aims at keeping them interested in the topic throughout their reading and comprehension of the text to finally find their answers. The final activity asks students to get in groups and give a coronation speech role-playing as one of the monarchs. This activity asks them not only to work in groups, but also individually, depending on how students organize themselves to prepare their speeches. Of course, this activity is meant to act as a closure activity summarizing what they have learned throughout the material and the topic at hand.

Having briefly explained the activities contained in the material, and as explained previously, I will now provide more detail about different characteristics and factors such as the learning objectives, skills, and structures mentioned before which were taken into account when designing this material.

Table 1*Characteristics of "The Tudors" material (Appendix 1)*

Learning outcomes	
Objectives	<p>To learn about the main events of the Tudor Age.</p> <p>To learn about each Tudor queen and king.</p> <p>To work in pairs and exchange information and opinions about the main problems of the Tudor Age.</p> <p>To learn about the significance of the events of the Tudor Age.</p> <p>To make predictions based on images, readings and discussions.</p> <p>To learn about the main achievements of each king and queen during their reign.</p> <p>To evaluate reading comprehension skills.</p> <p>To practice roleplay.</p> <p>To make and give speeches based on what was learned.</p>
Topic Content	<p>Main events of the Tudor Age and their significance.</p> <p>Tudor kings and queens</p> <p>Main problems of the Tudor Age</p> <p>Principal achievements of each Tudor king and queen during their reign.</p>
Key Competences	<p>Cooperation</p> <p>Working in pairs</p> <p>Working individually</p> <p>Communication in a foreign language</p> <p>Personal initiative</p> <p>Learning to learn</p> <p>Social competence</p>
Student Interpersonal Communication Learning	
Vocabulary	<p>Nouns: dynasty, throne, claim, recognition, monarchy, policy, foundation, power, shipbuilding, rulers, sacraments, chivalry, etc.</p>

Verbs: lay, strengthen, transform, proclaim, abolish, enforce, vanish, remain, execute, remarry, etc.

Adjectives: dynastic, foreign, naval, elite, elder, popular, unified, powerful, disappointed, domestic, etc.

Discourse markers: so, as, and, when, also, but, etc.

Structures	Making promises with going to and will Comparative and superlative structures Giving an opinion (I think... In my opinion... etc.) Past Simple and Past Perfect Expressing agreement or disagreement
Language skills	Speaking (Productive skill). Individual and pair work. Reading (Receptive skill)

Organization of tasks and activities

Tasks and activities	Activity 1: warm up matching activity about some of the main events during the Tudor period. Pictures: Visual aids Activity 2: follow up speaking activity about the same topic, this time asking and sharing opinions in pairs. Activity 3: reading comprehension about Henry VII, Henry VIII, Mary I, and Elizabeth I. Genre: Biographic. Matching activity according to what was read previously in the texts. Match the correct king/queen with the statements. Activity 4: Students revisit what they have discussed in activity 2 and check if their predictions were right or wrong.
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Activity 5: Speaking activity which involves individual as well as group work and whole class work. Students present a coronation speech by role playing a specific king or queen. The information used can be found in all of the previous activities they have done.

Instructions and considerations for teachers

One thing teachers should bear in mind is that these activities can be preceded or followed up by other resources discussing the same or similar topics. In this case, this material was used as a summary after students had read about the Tudor dynasty in their course material, namely, "An Illustrated History of Britain". However, other resources have also proven to be useful, as TedTalks, TedEd, PowerPoint presentations, videos, images, etc.

In the first activity, students are stimulated by the use of visual aids which can be a good warm up for what they are about to read and do in the follow up activities. Some of the principal events of the Tudor era are discussed and students get an overall picture. This can be done individually or as a whole-class activity. At the same time, it doesn't present much difficulty, as each fact is very distinct from the other, it would not require more than 5 minutes.

The second activity requires pair work and an exchange of information and opinions about the main problems of the Tudor Age. It also fosters the relationship between classmates, communication, as well as the practice of structures to ask and share opinions and ideas. This activity should take from 5 to 10 minutes maximum and teachers can ask students to share what they have discussed with the rest of the class or just move on with the next activity.

The third activity may be considered one of the most important ones, as the comprehension of the text is key for students to learn the topic and do the rest of the activities. After carefully reading the texts (this can be done individually or as a whole

class activity), students need to match each king/queen with the correct statement. This is a good way for students to summarize the main facts about each monarch. The activity should take between 10 to 15 minutes, and can be checked by teachers asking each student for the correct answer.

In the fourth activity, students revisit the predictions they made previously and find out if what they believed was right or wrong. Teachers will find out that some students already knew this information, others learned a little more and some needed the text to actually know what were the main problems the Tudors had to deal with. This activity can be checked in pairs as the second activity was done this way, however, the teacher can choose to discuss the question with the whole class. It shouldn't take more than 5 minutes.

Finally, in the fifth activity students are asked to work in groups and also (individually or in groups) prepare and give a coronation speech. This is a fun way for them to roleplay and actually summarize what achievements each monarch made during his/her reign. Moreover, they will practice using the vocabulary and structures they learned when reading the text. This activity should take from 15 to 20 minutes.

6.4 Elizabeth I

The second material to be discussed is "Elizabeth I" (Appendix 2). It consists of four activities about the Queen Elizabeth I, her many well-known portraits, greatest achievements and the overall principal events of the Elizabethan times.

The activities in this material for the most part focus on Elizabeth I and her portraits. However, another major goal and maybe the most important of this material, is for students to practice history-related vocabulary in the Use of English and multiple-choice exercise at the end of the unit.

When Elizabeth I claim to the throne after the death of Mary I, many in England rejoiced at having her as their new ruling monarch. However, underneath the optimism lay the strong discrimination that had endured for decades against female leaders. The overwhelming majority of the current subjects of Elizabeth claimed that women in almost every respect were inherently inferior to men. To find their own way through the world, they had neither the intellect nor the inner strength, according to many at the time. This is a fact that many students may not take into account when reading about the Tudor Age and if not mentioned explicitly, it may go unnoticed.

Through her portraits, Elizabeth I became the first queen to use her image to convey the power and aspirations of the crown, as well as establishing her as the head of the kingdom. They reflected Elizabeth in the light she wanted to portrait herself in, as a strong powerful monarch who was far from being inferior to men. Each portrait showed different characteristics of the queen's physical appearance and called upon the likeness of her subjects. This fact is not mentioned in the previous material, and I consider it to be interesting for students who may relate to this social issue. Feminism in Argentina has played a major role these past years trying to tackle major social and political issues. Students may soon make reference to this issue in class, comparing the English culture at the time with our own, along with their issues and our issues as well.

Having mentioned the relevance of the topic, I will proceed by briefly explaining the activities which play a role in students' learning during their implementation in this particular designed material. The first activity centers on students' visual intelligence, as they focus their attention on Elizabeth I's portraits taking into account their different elements. This is a warm-up activity which is meant to stimulate discussion in pairs among students, giving them a preview of what they will be learning in the unit. The second activity is similar to the second activity in the Tudor material, where students are required to make inferences about the reason why there are so many portraits of the queen. It also draws on the same skills and considerations mentioned previously in the second activity of the Tudor material. The third activity of the material centers on students comparing one portrait to the ones they have seen in activity 1, this continues the thematic of the unit using visual aids and also serves for students to draw some hints as to why there are so many portraits which share different or similar characteristics. The final activity, and perhaps the most important one of this material, as mentioned before focuses on students' vocabulary of the subject. With a multiple-choice activity, aiming to make inferences about the correct word choice easier on them, students revise and learn

new words which can help in their understanding and production skills throughout the English History course.

Having shortly described the tasks found in the content of this topic, and as previously described, I will now include more information on various characteristics and considerations such as the already stated learning aims, abilities, and processes that were taken into consideration while developing this material.

Table 2

Characteristics of “Elizabeth I” material (Appendix 2)

Learning outcomes	
Objectives	<p>To learn about the portraits of Queen Elizabeth I.</p> <p>To learn about Queen Elizabeth, I and the events of the Elizabethan Age.</p> <p>To compare different portraits of Queen Elizabeth I, taking aspects like clothes, colors and lines into account.</p> <p>To work in pairs and exchange information and opinions about the portraits of the queen.</p> <p>To make predictions based on images, readings and discussions.</p> <p>To evaluate reading comprehension skills.</p> <p>To evaluate specific subject vocabulary by using use of English activities.</p>
Topic Content	<p>Characteristics of Queen Elizabeth I’s portraits.</p> <p>How different portraits of the queen may differ from each other and why.</p> <p>Some aspects of Queen Elizabeth I’s life</p>
Key Competences	<p>Cooperation</p> <p>Working in pairs</p> <p>Working individually</p> <p>Communication in a foreign language</p> <p>Learner autonomy</p> <p>Learning to learn</p>

Student Interpersonal Communication Learning

Vocabulary	<p>Nouns: monarchy, crown, throne, royalty, voyage, portraits, kindness, loyalty, devotion, success, nobility, etc.</p> <p>Verbs: held, keep, take, capture, take, get, reach, shine, avoid, protect, labor, etc.</p> <p>Adjectives: safe, certain, sure, confident, healthy, pale, tanned, sick, delicate, rich, poor, mythical, wealthy, majesty, etc.</p> <p>Adverbs: majestically, colorfully, poorly, simply, etc.</p> <p>Discourse markers: first, last, when, however, instead, perhaps, while, etc.</p>
Structures	<p>Comparative and superlative structures</p> <p>Making inferences and predictions (I predict... My guess is... I infer... Perhaps... This could mean... etc.)</p> <p>Giving an opinion (I think... In my opinion... etc.)</p> <p>Past Simple and Past Perfect</p> <p>Expressing agreement or disagreement</p>
Language skills	<p>Speaking (Productive skill). Individual and pair work.</p> <p>Reading (Receptive skill)</p>

Organization of tasks and activities

Tasks and activities	<p>Activity 1: warm up speaking activity about Queen Elizabeth I's appearance in the portraits showed. Students find similarities in their appearance.</p> <p>Pictures: Visual aids</p>
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Activity 2: follow up speaking activity about the same topic, this time asking and making inferences/predictions in pairs based on the conversation they had before.

Activity 3: speaking activity about a different portrait of the queen, this time comparing it to the ones discussed in Activity 1.

Picture as visual aid.

Activity 4: Reading comprehension and multiple-choice activity about what students have discussed in the other activities, as well as additional information about the Queen.

Instructions or considerations for teachers

In the first activity, students are able to practice their oral skills with a classmate and exchange different opinions and ideas based on the visual aids. They practice using comparative and superlative structures as well as descriptive sentences by taking into account the lines, clothes, and colors of the portraits. This activity should take from 5 to 10 minutes, and can be evaluated by the teacher asking different pairs for their opinions.

In the second activity, students make inferences and predictions about the reasons why there are so many portraits of the queen. These predictions may or may not be asserted, but the goal of the activity is for them to exchange their views and discuss a question related to what they have talked about before in pairs. This activity should take from 5 to 10 minutes, and can be evaluated by the teacher asking different pairs for their opinions.

In the third activity, students are asked to look at a different portrait of the queen and compare it to the ones they saw in activity 1. This activity can be done individually or in pairs. The goal is for students to notice how in the first pictures the queen was portrait majestic, mature, and more monarch-like, than in this portrait. This activity along with activity 1 and activity 2, can serve as a warm-up for what students will read in activity 4. Teachers should give students from 5 to 10 minutes to come up with a well-rounded comparison between the portraits and their

characteristics. This can be done in pairs or individually, depending on the goal of the teacher for that class.

As mentioned before, the last activity is related to what students have discussed previously in the other activities. It links the skills of reading comprehension as well as subject-related vocabulary. This activity should take from 10 to 15 minutes. Students may not be aware of all the words in bold, teachers may allow them to use a dictionary or in turn, use their inferencing skills to know which adjective, adverb, nouns, etc. they need to use to make the text coherent. This activity would be better done individually, as students have already worked in pairs in the previous activities, and would benefit from the self-evaluation.

6.5 The Victorian Age

The third material to be discussed is “The Victorian Age” (Appendix 3). It consists of five activities about the Victorian Age, the Victorian compromise, the social classes and code of conduct of the time.

This material mainly focuses on teaching students how to convert certain words related to the subject into different types of words, either converting a noun into an adjective, a verb into an adverb and so on. Students once more practice their reading comprehension but this time accompanied with the skill of completing the gaps with the correct form of the words in brackets. This may be conceivably the most important activity of all of the material. It is also preceded and followed by other activities which are meant to complement and deliver efficacy to the one mentioned before.

One of the most important topics in the curriculum of the subject and In English history is the Victorian Age, the time between around 1820 and 1914, corresponds approximately but not precisely to the duration of the reign of Queen Victoria (1837-1901). It was a time dominated by a class-based culture, a rising number of citizens eligible to vote, a rising government and economy, and the position of Britain as the world's most strong empire. That was the period of the first Industrial Revolution in the nations, Charles Dickens and Charles Darwin, political progress and cultural reform, a railroad boom and the first telephone and telegraph.

When a student looks for information or reads about the Victorian Age in History books, most find out about the facts mentioned previously. Most times History teachers talk about the great accomplishments derived from the Victorian Age and moderately mention some of the disadvantages of those who were under privileged and had to suffer the conditions in working factories, hunger and other social, political and economic issues. However, when designing this material, I wanted my students to focus on something different than the most well-known facts they have already read in their coursebooks and which could result in having deeper discussions about the English culture at the time. For that reason, this material places emphasis on Victorian values and the compromise society had to make in order to obey them and be accepted in society itself.

The word "Victorian" nowadays denotes a prudent unwillingness to accept the presence of sex, hypocritically coupled with endless sexual conversations, loosely disguised as a series of warnings. Both aspects of this stereotypes have some validity to them. A few Victorians who were educated wrote a lot about women, including pornography, medical treatises, and psychiatric research. In fact, respectable middle-class women were proud of just how little they learned about their own sexuality and reproduction. Many of them never even spoke of sex. Furthermore, until the end of the century, Victorians lived with a sexual double standard that hardly anyone ever challenged. This along with other "Victorian values" are discussed in the text students are required to read and may arise many comments and discussions from students, comparing their own culture and values with the ones from the Victorian Age.

The material starts by asking students to once again, like in the other materials, make inferences about the meaning of the word "compromise" and to relate it to the Victorian Age. This is done as a warm up that can consequently involve students in recalling what they have learned about the topic already and generate interest in it. Next, the second activity aims at allowing students to find out if their predictions were correct by reading the text that follows, ignoring the gaps in it. The third activity focuses on getting students to use their abilities in order to convert nouns into adjectives and vice versa. Some of these will be useful for the following activity and students will benefit from learning new vocabulary. The next activity asks students to fill in the gaps with the correct form of the words in brackets. Learners will in turn have to read the text once more and find out if they need an adjective, noun, verb, adverb, etc. according to the sentence in which it finds itself. The last activity from the material sums up what students have learned about,

asking them to reflect upon four questions related to what they read in the text from Activity 2.

After briefly discussing the tasks included in the content of this section, I will now provide more detail on different characteristics and factors, such as the already mentioned learning objectives, skills, and processes that were taken into account during the creation of this material.

Table 3

Characteristics of “The Victorian Age” material (Appendix 3)

Learning outcomes	
Objectives	<ul style="list-style-type: none"> To learn about the Victorian compromise To learn about the Victorian Age To learn about the values present in Victorian times. To practice the conversion of some nouns into adjectives and vice versa. To learn and practice History-related vocabulary To learn about the Victorian social classes and their code of values. To evaluate reading comprehension skills. To make predictions and answer questions about a text.
Topic Content	<ul style="list-style-type: none"> The Victorian compromise The Victorian Age Victorian social classes Code of values of the Victorian Age Different type of words related to the topic.
Key Competences	<ul style="list-style-type: none"> Working individually Communication in a foreign language Autonomy and personal initiative Brainstorming Learning to learn Cultural awareness and expression Digital competence (Internet as possible resource)

Student Interpersonal Communication Learning

Vocabulary	<p>Nouns: stability, comfort, charity, prudery, owner, duty, respect, punishment, manifestation, etc.</p> <p>Adjectives: dutiful, respectful, patriarchal, chaste, distinguished, widespread, marginated, etc.</p> <p>Verbs: promote, reflect, want, refined, distinguish, imply, address, absorb, dominate, suffer, repress, etc.</p>
Structures	<p>Passive Voice</p> <p>Comparative and superlative structures</p> <p>Making inferences and predictions (I predict... My guess is... I infer... Perhaps... This could mean... etc.)</p> <p>Giving an opinion (I think... In my opinion... etc.)</p> <p>Past Simple</p>
Language skills	<p>Speaking (Productive skill)</p> <p>Reading (Receptive skill)</p> <p>Writing (Productive skill)</p>

Organization of tasks and activities

Tasks and activities	<p>Activity 1: SPEAKING/WRITING - warm up activity where students are asked to brainstorm the meaning of the word “compromise” and infer how it is related to the Victorian Age.</p> <p>Activity 2: READING - Students are asked to read a text about the Victorian age and check if the predictions they made in Activity 1 are correct.</p> <p>Activity 3: VOCABULARY – Students are asked to complete a table with the correct noun or adjective of each word.</p>
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Activity 4: VOCABULARY/READING – Afterwards, students read the text again and use the words in capitals to form a new word (it may be an adjective, adverb, etc.) to complete the gaps and the overall text.

Activity 5: WRITING/READING COMPREHENSION – Students answer questions about the text they have read in Activity 2.

Instructions or considerations for teachers

In the first activity, teachers should bear in mind that students should have some previous knowledge about the Victorian Age in order to relate the word “compromise” to the topic. If students don’t know the meaning of the word, they may use the Internet, dictionaries, etc. and then brainstorm together the different meanings and connotations of the word. Teachers may ask students to write their answers and then discuss them orally, or just answer them orally. This activity can be done either individually or in groups, and may be checked orally by the teacher. It should take from 5 to 10 minutes depending on the students’ previous knowledge about the topic.

In the second activity, students are asked to do a reading comprehension activity and check if the predictions they made previously are correct. Teachers may allow students to have a dictionary or the Internet at hand, since there may be a lot of new subject-related words for some students. Teachers should also tell students to ignore the blank spaces in the text and just read to have a general idea of the text. This can take from 5 to 15 minutes depending on the students’ level of English and previous knowledge. After reading, teachers may ask students if their predictions were right or wrong.

In the third activity, students practice making noun and adjective conversions. This can also be done with the resource of a dictionary or the Internet at hand. It should take from 5 to 10 minutes and can be checked by teachers asking students to

come to the front and write the answers on the board, orally, or in pairs.

In the fourth activity, students are asked to complete the gaps with the correct form of the words in capitals. This activity also allows them to practice the conversion of words into nouns, adjectives, adverbs, etc. Some words from Activity 3 may be found in the text also, teachers should bear in mind that some students may take longer than others to complete the activity. It should take from 10 to 15 minutes and at the end, the teacher can ask students to read one or two sentences each to check their pronunciation of the new words and reading/speaking skills.

In the last activity, teachers are able to check students' comprehension of the text, as they are asked to answer questions related to what they have read in Activity 2. Some students may attempt to make comparisons between the Victorian code of values and today's society values, teachers should take advantage of this opportunity, as it fosters students' interest on the topic. This activity can be done individually or in pairs, and should take from 10 to 15 minutes. It would be wise to ask students to write their answers, as they can practice using the vocabulary and structures they learned previously. The teacher can then check orally the answer of students by asking each of them to respond to a certain question. Then, teachers may ask students their opinion about the Victorian Age and summarize their main ideas about the principal characteristics of the time.

6.6 Further considerations and analysis

After having explained each of the materials on their own, I will now move on to talk about the three materials as a whole, considering factors and characteristics which were mentioned in my methodology and theoretic background that influenced my choices when designing them. As it can be noticed above, the materials share a wide variety of characteristics between them, these will be covered below. Also, I will provide more

information and further considerations teachers and as well as students may consider useful.

In CLIL, subject teachers are able to take advantage of language learning materials and opportunities which draw on the communicative approach. Moreover, with these materials learners have the opportunity to develop their linguistic and cognitive skills by implementing the proposed framework as they develop and explain their experiences, ideas, tasks, etc. As seen earlier, Jeyasala (2014) considers that educators ought to encourage students' communicative competence continually, and aside from their limitations to use language in a fluent and accurate manner, they should make spaces available to them to interact with others or to immerse them in speaking activities which in turn enhance their ability to use the target language. I believe this was done throughout the lessons where the CLIL designed materials were implemented.

These activities were designed following a Communication Approach to CLIL, this can be seen throughout the activities which foster the communicative competence for a given socio-cultural background, where students should be able to create grammatically correct sentences that can be understood, as well as use correct language forms, and eventually be able to make full utterances.

By doing these activities, learners also practice using a variety of structures, namely, making predictions or inferences, giving and asking for opinions, showing agreement or disagreement, and making comparisons among others. Inference skills are used throughout the curriculum, including English language arts, science, and social studies. Because inferencing requires higher-order thinking skills, many students will find it challenging. However, by doing some of the activities designed, those skills can be practiced and perfected. Regarding most of the skills asked from students, it is hoped that the materials promote the communication skills of students, and apart from their restrictions on using language in a fluent and precise way, they are designed to make spaces open to them to communicate with others or to immerse them in speaking exercises that in turn strengthen their ability to use the target language.

Of course, the key content of a language course is language. For the CLIL approach, though, there are other areas that should be integrated into the material and proposal of the course. Other characteristics exist, such as the emphasis on education and understanding from students and the importance on social context. This ensures that a teacher can teach other skills and information about a certain sociocultural background

and the way in which students learn, in addition to language. For that reason, these activities were also designed taking into account that CLIL contains contexts and resources that enhance the perception of the learner of their own society and that of others. Intercultural awareness and global citizenship are strengthened by every CLIL context. As one of the four CLIL values in motion, Coyle refers to cultural goals. Inside the community, it promotes teamwork, support, and appreciation. Pair and community work encourage children to interact and exchange interests in activities. That is why in many exercises, such as giving opinions and inferring about the topics, include teamwork and knowledge exchange between pupils.

Each subject material presents visual aids in order to improve the impact of the materials, as they are proven to be a very powerful tool. Words and images presented in various formats appeal directly to the imagination of students, adding power to a teacher's spoken words. The images present in the materials can be found easily in Google Images when typing the words "The Tudors", "Queen Elizabeth I" and "The Victorian Age".

The process of designing materials is really to make choices and to plan the quality of the lesson and the proposal at the most concrete stage. Material creation for a teacher who plans a lesson involves designing, selecting or modifying, and arranging resources and events so that students can accomplish the goals that will help them achieve the course's objectives. The teacher may either work with a current already created material (or a collection of materials) or create all the materials from scratch, or any combination of the two above. In this case, the activities in these materials were created from scratch, many times adapting Wikipedia texts in order for the activity to comply with the learning objectives set. This was done by changing words, using synonyms, opposites, shortening texts, inserting specific sentences which fitted the grammar objectives (mostly comparatives, superlatives, and sentences in past tenses), along with other adaptations for the purpose of improving learners' use of the language and reading comprehension.

Another consideration to take into account is that the activities in these materials are meant to promote academic proficiency, as explained before, by allowing students to learn new subject-related words (monarchy, reign, kingship, kingdom, heir, throne, etc.) present throughout all tasks, either using their receptive or productive skills. The materials also encourage learners to be autonomous in their own learners, that's why many of the activities present in them are meant to be done individually. Moreover, the

materials presented provide authentic language and urges learners to use it, since most of the texts meant to be read are taken or adapted from the Wikipedia site.

When giving instructions, as the teacher I demonstrated how the learners need to do the activities while providing guidance. How to fill the gaps, how to complete the table, or how to shape the questions for a speaking assignment, were some of the activities' instructions students were guided through the materials. I consider this to be fundamental since teachers often expect learners through verbal instructions alone to comprehend an activity. Not only does this confuse learners, but it also consumes valuable lesson time, as the educator must then repeat the instructions to the entire class or to individual tables.

The activities in these materials also aim to foster critical thinking, as they are not based on straightforward repetition but rather higher order thinking, creation, analysis, application and understanding. This along with taking into account the personal interest of learners, are powerful elements which can help fulfill the objectives described previously to design material fit to these learners' needs.

When they build their own questions and fully engage in the class, CLIL lets learners become more autonomous. Via partner and group practice, students voluntarily and collaboratively engage in the learning process. The teacher acts mostly like a facilitator who directs the learning process. This can be seen in activities like Activity 5 from the material "The Victorian Age", where some students may attempt to make comparisons between the Victorian code of values and today's society values apart from just answering questions about the text they were asked to read.

CLIL also contains contexts and resources that enhance the perception of the learner of their own society and that of others. Intercultural awareness and global citizenship are strengthened by every CLIL context. As previously discussed, Coyle refers to cultural aims as one of the four CLIL principles in action. Inside the community, it promotes teamwork, support, and appreciation. Pair and group work encourage students to interact and exchange their interests in activities. This can also be seen in the activity previously mentioned, along with for example, Activity 4 in "The Tudors" material, as it requires cooperation and the sharing of information to prepare and give a coronation speech.

In all of the materials, students are asked to make inferences or predictions, this can be linked to the learning to learn competence discuss previously. CLIL includes rich input

and accelerates the development of a variety of techniques for language acquisition, including the recognition of key words and cognates. Using prior knowledge to predict content is typical of CLIL activities. In these activities, learners ask themselves questions such as “what do I think I know about Elizabeth I?” and “what do I know about The Tudors so far?”. They also make predictions about the meaning of key terms, such as the meaning of “compromise” from Activity 1 in “The Victorian Age” and create connections between their own language and English.

Another important point to make, is that a large number of academic situations is encouraged throughout these activities so that students can work both in pairs and in groups, express their opinions with trust, and where various points of view are encountered. Learners are asked to perform a vast number of tasks in which, with no correct or wrong responses, they must express their views. I hope to create an inviting and responsive environment with this kind of approach, where learners take the lead role in the learning process. All of the above relates to the emotional competence which implies an ease around others and defines one's capacity to lead and express oneself effectively and successfully.

Along with this competence, students are also asked to implement their linguistic competence at all times. CLIL promotes the use of L2 in class as a medium of communication and students learn to treat English as the medium for the acquisition of the content of the materials. It is important in the classroom that students have the language they need to accomplish their work, since the real success of CLIL depends on providing them with this functional language. In addition, learners are taught how to properly explore ideas about the Tudors, Elizabeth I, and the Victorian Age throughout these materials, both by vocabulary and activities based on abilities such as reading, writing, and speaking.

One of the objectives of these materials was to make progress visible. Progress can be made by diligent preparation. Language, material and learning abilities in general may be split down into smaller units and expected results in the long term and short term. One major factor which plays an important role before students start working with the materials designed is that they are introduced to the defined objectives explained previously. This is because it is assumed that in order to accomplish them, students first need to know and appreciate the goals set. With my students, I explained to them what the objectives of each material were, and they had a clear understanding of the goal of the subject since they were also mentioned in the subject curriculum they are required

to read. As a result, I believe they were more motivated and did not present as many problems understanding what was required from them as if I hadn't explained the learning objectives before they began working with the designed material.

As mentioned before in this paper, one of the most crucial ones is what content learners will revisit and what content will be new to them. They need to be exposed to subject-specific language more than once, for that reason, revisiting a new concept is necessary. To revisit certain concepts, teachers should present learners with different tasks that demand several language skills but that are aimed at communication of the same concepts. Moreover, teachers should also note any anticipated difficulties learners may have with content and language learning while planning. This was taken into consideration when designing the activities contained in each material, specifically with reading-comprehension and use of English activities.

As mentioned previously, the language in CLIL is viewed through the content, and grammar and vocabulary are considered as a part of discourse rather than "*isolated fragments*" (Richards and Rodgers, 2001, p.208). The vocabulary students were exposed to had to be a mix between subject-related vocabulary and words they knew and used every day in their other course subjects, such as Grammar, English Language, Discourse Analysis, etc. Furthermore, these words did not have to be too far-fetched, that is, they had to be words students could find in their History books and resources, which they could later use in communication without much trouble. Accordingly, I tried to design the activities in the materials for that purpose, as it was also one of the learning objectives present at the beginning of the design stage.

Designing and applying CLIL is not a straightforward process, as we have learned, by using this approach there are many obstacles that history teachers face and need to address. History teachers, for instance, should feel confident about their level of English, especially if they haven't used English for a while (which luckily was not my case). As a teacher I had to be able to use effective vocabulary in the virtual classroom to address concerns in history, to challenge, paraphrase, inspire, explain and manage my group of students. In addition, in a transparent and factual way, students had to be able to present and analyze historical facts and references.

6.7 Evaluation: Formative assessment

Bear in mind that learning is a process in which results represent the competencies of students in a variety of subjects; all activities in this material will be assessed according to content rather than language-oriented, respecting the school syllabus and the material for that academic term. Evaluations are often much more than offering an end-of-unit exam or planning for a standardized examination. At both times, tests help form the learning experience, and give you visibility into student learning. An assessment of the planned activities provides the information to grade the success of the students; in addition, the feedback upon the completion of the materials will provide a clear picture of the competence of the students in the subject.

A key concern is that there is formative as well as summative evaluation in CLIL subjects and also the consistency in how learners are assessed through subjects in each school. Even though previously it had been said that CLIL could both have a summative and formative evaluation, taking into account the objectives and materials of this paper, a formative assessment is applied. It should be borne in mind that students are exposed to summative assessments throughout the year by doing their graded assignments and exams.

It may also be useful to remember what Black & William, (2009, p.7) claim:

Practice in a classroom is formative to the extent that evidence about student achievement is elicited, interpreted, and used by teachers, learners, or their peers, to make decisions about the next steps in instruction that are likely to be better, or better founded, than the decisions they would have taken in the absence of the evidence that was elicited.

The aim of formative evaluation is to track student learning and provide educators and students with ongoing feedback. It's a learning test. If properly structured, it enables students to recognize their strengths and weaknesses, enabling students to develop their self-regulatory abilities to handle their education in a less haphazard manner than is currently seen with summative assessments. It also provides the educators with knowledge about the areas which students are struggling with in order to put in place appropriate support. Formative tests help teachers understand the learning of students when teaching and change their teaching methods accordingly. Meaningful learning requires new information being processed, expectations changed and complex conclusions made.

Formative evaluation can be tutor-led, peer-led or self-assessment. Formative tests have low stakes and typically have no score, which may encourage and motivate students since they are not confronted with the stress they typically encounter in graded assignments and exams. This is fundamental since this group of students are beginning to start their courses and do not possess previous knowledge about what tertiary education is like. COVID-19, confinement and the shift between face-to-face to virtual classes have also played their part in making students feel unsure about their abilities, that is why formative assessment was finally decided upon the implementation of the materials.

It is clear to students that they obtain confidence in their tests by dealing with formative assignments, risk-free, and can develop far stronger skills in order to gain better grades in the summative evaluations. In this case, students' performance was evaluated by how they did the activities designed, which counted as the feedback I collected as a teacher. For students, formative assessments serve to evaluate their own learning, build knowledge, identify strengths and weaknesses, and improve their learning. For teachers, they serve to monitor students' learning, ascertain progress, check understanding and teach responsively.

As previously stated in this paper, it is important to link the assessment of learning, that is the formative assessment, to the attainment of learning outcomes for the lessons. Assessment criteria can be transparent. In this case, one learning outcome could be "Most learners should know that the Age of Enlightenment happened during the 18th century" or "Most learners should explain some events and changes during the Tudor times using source materials". However, an assessment could be "Most learners can summarize aspects of 18th-century life".

The evaluation of the materials, as said previously, was based on the students' response to them during class. There were three tools from formative assessments that were used to serve this purpose:

- Observation: the observation of students as they work and analysis of the feedback, they provide from the activities in order to check for learning. Observing students studying individually, in groups, or through whole-group learning will provide useful information on the development, comprehension, abilities and difficulties, teamwork, research patterns, and attitude of students.

- Self-assessment: A procedure in which students gather their own learning information, evaluate what it shows about their progress towards the expected learning objectives, and prepare the next steps in their learning.
- Oral Questioning: Effective questioning requires the use of classroom questions to open debates, encourage critical intellectual thinking, and facilitate engagement between students. In a student's response, appropriate questions concentrate on eliciting the process, i.e. the 'how' and 'why,' as opposed to responses that only detail 'what.'

More often than not, these assessment tools were used simultaneously or interchangeably during classes. The way in which these tools were implemented and the results encountered will be developed in the following section.

6.8 Results of the materials' implementation in class

Content and Language Integrated Learning poses many challenges to everyone involved in language training, from policymakers to teachers, as the decisions to be made in relation to its implementation cover all aspects of the curriculum.

The implementation of a CLIL methodology is not easy. The coordination of conceptual, procedural and linguistic contents is hard to achieve, as it is difficult to strike a balance to cover the three of them simultaneously. This complexity makes it harder to make decisions on the topics to be dealt with, the focus of the class, the material to be used, among other factors. The Holy Trinity of CLIL is certainly something to bear in mind when planning a lesson, a unit, or a complete language course. However, when implemented, it can encourage the use of “innovative methods in schools which directly address motivation, cognitive challenge, using languages to learn as well as learning to use the language” (Funiber, 2016, p.42).

The aim of this paper was mainly the design of CLIL materials for English History lessons, targeted at a specific group of students. However, as a teacher I wanted to test these materials and evaluate how my students responded to them in our lessons. I was curious as to notice if students encountered any actual benefits or drawbacks during the implementation of the three materials as opposed to believing blindly in the benefits of

CLIL exposed theoretically. For that purpose, and as explained before, the evaluation of the materials designed was driven by the use of three formative assessment tools: observation, self-assessment and oral questioning. These tools are part of formative evaluation practices which are used to measure the knowledge of content, cognitive and linguistic competence, and involvement in academic achievement of students. These evaluation practices enable teachers to track the learning of students so that they can adjust instruction accordingly, provide accurate and relevant feedback to students, and encourage learners to reflect on their own cognitive learning.

As I explain my results and analysis, I will not get into specific detail on each observation from each activity, but give an overall picture of my findings. This will be done by focusing on some of the results from some of the activities I consider give a fundamental picture of how the material succeeded or not in aiming at the goals previously established.

6.8.1 Observations

During their day-to-day teaching, most teachers use classroom observations. The problem is how to systematically arrange and document the findings and to make efficient use of the results. Without a cohesive structure, the findings of teachers run the risk of being scattered and thus less valuable pedagogically.

The relation of student results with performance expectations shows the degree to which these targets are accomplished by students. If we want the analogy to be a useful one, teachers need to concentrate their observations mainly on demonstrating the skills listed in the course. Focusing observations in this way makes observations in the classroom manageable and comprehensive since the target of observation is established and delineated. It is possible to interpret systematic observation of student success as 'tests'. Therefore, these knowledge acquisition techniques can have the same properties as important tests.

In observing this particular group of students, I mainly focused on watching for frustration (if students could not work on their own, needed extra help or gave up doing an activity) and boredom (if the student felt the material and the activities were too easy). It is known that when the content of the materials is higher than the student's level, the teacher should adapt the material in order for all students to participate and gain knowledge from the lesson. This was done in some of the texts students encountered, which were authentic texts taken out from Wikipedia. While observing students in my online class, I

noticed that most of them were more enthusiastic when doing pair or group work activities rather than individual activities.

By making observations, teachers have a better idea of how to help the student improve in the subject or how to adapt the design material to involve him/her more. There are several means of documenting observations that you make. To jot down your ideas, use sticky notes and then post them on a poster with the names of your pupils, plan a checklist of items you want to look at as students work, or keep a folder written on self-stick labels or sheets of paper with records of your findings. In my case, I documented by observation in my notebook aiming at writing down some of the positive and negative responses towards the materials.

There were not many students who got frustrated when doing the activities, if there was something that they did not know, they followed up with the next activity they had to do and chose to revisit the last activity later on. Many students are taught this “strategy” during their high school years, where teachers during evaluations or tasks, tell students to move on with the next activity if they get frustrated with a particular one. Then, they can go back and do the activity more calmly with a fresh start. This can be helpful for learners who often get “stuck” in an activity and cannot move on from it. It is mostly beneficial during exams, where there are great amounts of pressure for students to do well and there is the time-constraint factor to it.

On many occasions, students switched English to Spanish when they got frustrated as they could not remember a particular English word, especially those related to the new subject material. This was expected to happen, since as I mentioned previously, moving between L1 and the target language, either mid-sentence or between sentences is quite common for learners in CLIL. This is known as code switching, which was mentioned and briefly explained formerly in this paper. The use of L1 and the target language happens when clarifying teachers’ instructions, developing ideas for curricular content, off-task social comments, encouraging peers, and group negotiations among others. It is also said to happen when students (as well as teachers) want to address a complex topic, build rapport or further clarify any instructions. In this case, students used the L1 when trying to communicate with peers during speaking activities or when they were trying to give an opinion or make a question about what they had read. Unless teachers find themselves in a situation where using the L1 could benefit or reassure learners, it is important that they avoid using regularly in class. This means teachers should be able to justify their use of L1.

Although code-switching can have positive benefits, it should be done in moderation and teachers should be clear with students in what situations they are allowed to code-switch. Besides, as users and teachers of English, one of our main goals is to aim for as much immersion of the second language as possible. Instead of code-switching, teachers may provide alternatives, such as pre-teaching vocabulary thoroughly, providing plenty of comprehensible input, make use of cognates and foster a supportive classroom environment.

Taking what was said above into consideration, I preceded responding to their questions or comments asking other classmates if they knew how those words were said in English. I also resorted to letting them speak freely in communication activities, only correcting those students who were using too much Spanish. After certain tasks I resorted to using PowerPoint presentations with visual aids for students to notice what new words they had learned or revised. This can also be done in a number of different ways; I found this the easier to do considering the time students had in every class. A picture, a word, and a definition of that word after a task which focuses a lot on vocabulary may be beneficial for learners to sum up and revise what they have learned. Activities such as Activity 3 from the Tudors' material, Activity 2 from the Victorian Age's material and Activity 4 from the Elizabeth I's material can be taken as the main activities where students used code-switching.

Students did not get bored as most of the content was challenging for them. However, I observed that when they felt the content was above their knowledge, they could turn to their peers or the Internet in order to work out the specific problem they were facing. For example, in Activity 1 from the material "The Victorian Age", many students became discouraged after researching the meaning of the word "compromise", since they had to infer how it could be related to the Victorian Age. Many could not predict how this word could be related to the Victorian Age and wanted to move on to Activity 2 instead to find out. However, the goal of that question was for students to practice making inferences and predictions, so I insisted that they come up with an idea of how the word could be related to the topic, even if they did not believe their predictions were correct. This strategy was proven successful, as at the end of the activity every student had made a prediction. So, in the end, when taking into consideration how much frustration or boredom students experienced during my observations, it could be said that they were successful in becoming engaged with the materials and persevere when encountering a setback.

6.8.2 Self-Assessment

Another formative assessment tool I chose to incorporate was self-evaluation, a process in which students evaluate themselves, motivates students to take more responsibility for their learning by, for example, facilitating taking part in evaluation criteria and getting involved with their own success. In more conventional activities, such as essays and lectures, you might use self-assessment in the form of retrospective exercises, such as logs or diaries, or by allowing the students to evaluate how well they have met the performance criterion. It is a fundamental tool that activates some deep reflection. Furthermore, the willingness to objectively learn of your own work lies at the top of Bloom's Taxonomy, in the "Evaluation" section.

In general, for the purpose of developing it, student self-assessment relates to teaching students to determine their own performance. Students need to have a specific objective, the ability to help build a concept of quality work, input and the chance to improve or self-adjust their answers before handing them in order to become competent assessors of their work.

By doing this self-evaluation, students can learn from their past errors, consider their strengths and shortcomings, and learn to appropriately target their learning. This knowledge will then be used by students to guide their potential jobs, whether in a language course or in education, by playing to their strengths and/or focusing their energies in areas that they have already identified as requiring more development. In this way, getting students to become more involved in their learning help transform the idea of learning as a passive process where they only listen to you and absorb the content to simply repeat during a certain task. They are more likely to get involved in their learning if students are observers rather than spectators during History lessons.

At the end of each one of the materials, I showed students five questions in a PowerPoint Presentation:

- What did you find interesting about the topic we worked on?
- In pair and group activities, did you feel more confident when doing the task at hand?
- Do you think after doing these activities you have a better comprehension of the subject?

- Did you learn new vocabulary and grammatical structures? If you did, what were they and did you put them into practice?
- Is there any concept or topic left that you can't grasp?

Students then, were given ten minutes to reflect upon these questions and self-assess their work and knowledge. After reading and reflecting upon these five questions, students were given the possibility to share their answers with me. As in self-assessment it is not mandatory for students to share their answers with the teacher, since it is a self-reflection activity for students to share their answers with others, I opted to give them the possibility to share their answers with me if they felt they wanted to do so. The majority of the students from the group participated in the discussion of these questions and generally each student responded a different question, that means students did not get to share their answers for all of the five questions.

The first question draws on how they felt about the topics chosen for the materials. The second one asked them to reflect upon their cooperation with their classmates and if they feel more confident working with them instead of individually. The third question is about their learning of the subject and if the materials actually succeeded in giving them a better comprehension of the topics. The fourth question asks students to analyze what they have learned about the English language rather than the History topic itself, and if they have put that knowledge into practice during the implementation of the materials. Finally, the fifth question serves to check students' understanding of the topics and review if there was any fact, word, information, etc. that was not understood properly. For the purpose of clarifying students' answers to each of the questions, the information will be displayed in the following table:

Table 4

Results from self-assessment questions given to students

Quest. N°	Self-assessment question	Results and answers from students
1	What did you find interesting about the topic we worked on?	Regarding the first question, most students commented that they found interesting certain facts such as how many wives Henry VIII had, why Mary I was called "Bloody Mary", how Elizabeth I was portrayed in her many portraits and the strictness of the Victorian code of conduct in England. I was not

taken by surprise by the responses to this question since throughout the years of teaching this subject most students provide similar answers. The most shocking or interesting History facts are often mentioned, along with facts that depict English life and culture very differently from our own.

2 In pair and group activities, did you feel more confident when doing the task at hand?

As to the second question, students gave mixed answers, some claiming to prefer and feel more confident in peer and group work activities rather than individual ones, and others claiming the contrary. I believe this may be because of their individual learning factors as well as personality. Some students from this group have more introvert competences and prefer working alone, others are more extrovert and would rather work on activities along with other classmates. Introverts can be just as sociable as their extroverted classmates, but to recharge, they need inner thinking at the end of the day. In a college course, this implies that introverts often enjoy the chance to look at course material at their own pace, at their own time. Extroverts feed away from external energy and communication with others, making it an awesome alternative for synchronous courses. In a live lesson of two dozen or more attendees, however, it can be hard to connect in a meaningful way with others. So, in the end, students' responses to this question come down to students' personality and preferences at the time of working on a certain task.

I should also mention that during virtual classes in COVID-19 lockdown, extroverts and introverts face distinct learning and social obstacles. Knowing what category suits them best and how to use their unique predilections to their advantage is crucial. Armed with these tips, in a virtual environment,

students can adapt their distinct learning styles for effective class engagement, analysis, and peer communication.

- 3 Do you think after doing these activities you have a better comprehension of the subject? The third question received an overall positive answer, as students expressed that after doing the activities from the designed materials, they felt they had a better understanding of the topics. This is not surprising, after all, they have been given more information and worked towards learning these history topics better as a result from their desire to pass the subject, but it is important to point out that learners could understand what was asked from them in each activity and could accomplish a satisfactory language and content level of understanding and application of them as well.
- 4 Did you learn new vocabulary and grammatical structures? If you did, what were they and did you put them into practice? Regarding the fourth question, most students claimed that what they learned the most was vocabulary rather than grammar. The majority of learners from the group expressed that the grammatical part of each material serves as good practice of what they were learning about the English language. One of the most mentioned examples of this was the use of comparatives and superlatives found in many of the text they had to read and speaking activities. However, they claimed that in a great number of activities, they had to turn to dictionaries, their classmates or the Internet to search the meaning of a variety of History-related words. The words they mentioned were the ones listed above in the description of the vocabulary of each material.

As a result of their search for the definitions of these new words, students learned new vocabulary

related to the subject and claimed they could put it into practice in activities that required them to practice their communication skills. There were two activities students mentioned the most when trying to exemplify this case, these were Activity 4 from the Tudor material (where they are asked to give a coronation speech as one of the Tudor monarchs) and Activity 5 from the Victorian Age material (where they were asked to answer some questions and implement the vocabulary they have learned).

- 5 Is there any concept or topic left that you can't grasp? As to the last question, the majority of students expressed that as the grammatical part of the materials was not new to them and the search of the new subject-related vocabulary words resulted in immediate knowledge and application of them, they felt they understood the topics well. Apart from this, it should be bore in mind that students already have some knowledge of the topics from the materials designed, as they have seen them in their coursebooks and other resources used to implement the content of the subject's curriculum. As a result, no student expressed to have found any difficulty in understanding a certain concept or fact they were exposed to in the materials. It may be added that because students shared their answers in a whole-class discussion, some may have felt embarrassed or worried about claiming they have not understood something when their peers had already expressed that they did not have any problems with the materials.

6.8.3. Questioning

Efficient questioning is a perfect way to get learners to think objectively and individually and to find some misunderstandings we could prevent as teachers. It is believed that

when one starts using it in the classroom, the change in interactions between students will soon be seen and lessons will be productive and useful for everyone.

As stated previously, a significant factor to take into account when planning a CLIL English History lesson or design materials for said lesson is the development of thinking skills. Teachers need to ask questions which encourage lower order thinking skills, that is according to Bloom's Taxonomy (Bloom, 1956, p.25), those skills include, "remembering, understanding, and applying" or the "what, when, where and which questions".

The growth of both thinking and listening skills also needs to be prepared ahead. Teachers should consider if, during the class, learners switch from lower to higher thinking ability. They need to prepare and also practice the kinds of questions they ask in order to improve all kinds of reasoning.

These are some of the benefits I encountered when using questioning after the implementation of the materials:

- Students were more encouraged with their work and each other: students got more engaged and motivated when asked about their work and their opinions about the materials. Sharing the ideas they developed from what they learned through their use of the materials as resources, proved to be reassuring and inspiring for the rest of the students when they provided answers individually and as pairs or groups.
- Students practiced thinking out loud: most of the time, teachers ask students to think for themselves and write answers according to what they read in some activity. By questioning them orally, it lets them think out loud and, on the spot, which is important for communicative purposes.
- Students felt empowered and confident about their opinions: by this active discussion, students felt that their ideas and opinions about the topic actually matter. Their peers got involved in whole-class discussions which also help students clarify their understanding and develop interest in the topics of the designed materials.

Questioning is similar to the interviewing process, the difference lies in that questioning is more informal, this is because questions can be asked as students work on an activity as the teacher circulates the classroom. These questions need to be effective, well-considered, and demanding to have the desired result. When questioning students, before, during, or after the implementation of the materials, I concentrated on providing closed and open questions. Closed questions are the most common in English lessons, as they prompt simple responses from students, either yes/no questions or short answers.

Some of the closed questions I asked during the implementation of the three design materials were:

- How many wives did Henry VIII have?
- What were the reasons for Henry VIII to murder most of his wives?
- Who was the first Tudor king?
- Was Mary I against the Protestants or Catholics?
- Did Mary I let Protestants live a peaceful life or did they experience repercussions because of their faith?
- Why was Elizabeth I called the "Virgin Queen"?
- Do you consider the Tudor dynasty was good towards England's prosperity?
- What did Queen Elizabeth I do to please her subjects?
- How was Queen Elizabeth depicted in her portraits?
- Who were the only surviving children of Henry VIII?
- Was Elizabeth I worried about religious groups during her reign?
- Did the strict code of conduct of the Victorian Age bring people stability?
- When was Mary I born?

The closed questions used, proved to have certain benefits. They were easy to respond to and usually reduced misunderstanding quickly and effectively. They were also particularly useful for challenging the memory of learners and remembering information. Students responded all closed questions correctly, as they felt confident in what they had read in the materials and deemed these questions to be easy to respond, moreover, the fact that much of what they learned was already discussed with their peers or studied at home provided them with confidence at the time of participating in class.

However, using only closed questions to get feedback from students' performance during the design activities was not enough, as they tend to limit the students' opportunity to

expand on their answers or make reasoning and opinions available. On the other hand, open questions involve a deeper level of thought and always prompt a longer answer. Students are asked to consider and reflect, have views and reactions, and take charge of the conversation.

Some of the open questions I asked during the implementation of the three design materials were:

- What did you think about Henry VIII after learning through the text you read that he had so many wives?
- Why do you think Henry VIII did not have many children?
- What message was Elizabeth I trying to give through her portraits?
- Would you say Elizabeth's message would have come across in our country as it did in England? Why / Why not?
- Describe the role of the Victorian code of conduct during the Victorian Age.
- What importance did Henry VII have on the prosperity of England?
- Taking into account what you learned about the Tudors, who in your opinion contributed the most towards England's welfare?
- How do you interpret Elizabeth's rejection to all her suitors?
- What possible benefits could Victorian values bring upon English society?
- Are there any Victorian values you are against? Why?
- In your opinion, how are Victorian values different from our society's?

The open questions implemented in class proved to be beneficial and by promoting individual thought, they improved the learning process of students. As a teacher, they also gave me the chance to review the comprehension and knowledge of these students, and test their ability to apply this knowledge. Because this type of questions asked students to be more thoughtful and extensive with their answers, rather than having them volunteer to answer the questions, I asked one at a time to the entire class and then picked one volunteer to answer.

At times, when I considered a question to be more difficult than the others, I opted to make students aware I was going to call upon them to answer, so they could prepare and think through what they were going to say. I found out that if I let students become aware that they had to answer a particular question, the class would have much higher level of engagement. In the end, this type of questions was more time consuming because students had to think more and provide more extensive answers than with close

questions. However, it was worth it as I could check students' understanding of the topics, which I deem satisfactory and adequate. On the other hand, by listening to their classmates' answers and opinions, students learned from each other and also became more encouraged to take part in discussions by providing their own ideas and opinions.

Every contribution from students was valuable, even though I thought some of the answers were not exactly correct or could be better explained. I chose to show appreciation for every response and gave suitable praise depending on the quality it. Using a follow-up question such as "How did you arrive to that conclusion?" or "If you consider *this fact*, would you still maintain your opinion?". This offered students the ability to think about their method of reasoning and helped me solve any misunderstanding they might have.

It should be bore in mind that open and closed questions are both helpful. Although open questions provide learners the chance to include insight and rationale, closed questions are helpful for fast fact checks and pushing the lesson forward. For that reason, I varied my questions and, depending on my justification for asking, use both open and closed questions. For example, if I wanted to rapidly verify that a student had recalled a fact, I asked a question like "How many wives did Henry VIII have?" or "Who was the first Tudor king?". On the other hand, using an open question such as "How are Victorian values different from our society's?" or "What importance did Henry VII have on the prosperity of England?", was best if I wanted a student to give their thoughts on something and initiate a class discussion on a certain subject. Because of all the benefits mentioned previously about both type of questions, students provided high quality answers which demonstrated they not only understood the topics but also managed to become motivated about them.

As I mentioned before, one of the main objectives of this paper was to learn and put into practice the design of CLIL materials for English History classes, however, I wanted to briefly comment on some of the results I came upon when implementing them. These results should not be taken as a full review of the materials' implementation with other students, as the target audience of these materials are considered a reduce group of 20 students, with specific similar characteristics such as language level, age, culture, among other context specific factors shared. For that reason, when implementing these materials, other positive or negative results could come up according to the group of students and the context in which they are implemented.

6.9 Benefits and drawbacks encountered

Up to now we have discussed the development of the designed materials, how they were evaluated and some of the results I encountered during their implementation. I have also mentioned other considerations teachers as well as students might take into account when using the materials, as well as justifying my design choices, such as the competences and skills students will need to put into practice, the font used, or the type of activities designed. Now I will talk about the benefits and drawbacks encountered from the above-mentioned results.

When looking at the issues students faced while using the designed materials, by looking at the formative tools used to assess them, the main problem was their use of code-switching when they did not have the necessary linguistic knowledge to express themselves. In addition, at the beginning students showed frustration when doing some of the activities from the materials along with tasks which required them to learn new subject-related vocabulary. If they felt they were forced to perform, students who were confused would easily become irritated in the online lesson. In some cases, I infer that concentration or processing problems might have stopped some learners from understanding a lesson, or not allowing them to be sure about the guidelines for a given task.

There could be more than one explanation why students felt overwhelmed, in this case I believe this frustration might have been connected with those students who had high success standards, such as trying to get the response right every time or delivering error-free writing/speaking that does not need revisions. It is important to remember that precisely the same techniques would not benefit the same learners. Frustration will cause students to lose interest over time. This can lead to increased anxiety, a loss of trust, poor self-esteem, and a pessimistic approach to school and learning. Moreover, students are more inclined to self-soothe in the future by being able to model positive methods of addressing frustration they were taught in class.

For teachers such as myself to decide whether the dissatisfaction is fleeting or has become a long-term concern, is fundamental. In this case, I believe their frustration was short-term, since when implementing tools to help them overcome it, they quickly realized they could solve this issue and move on with the tasks, being motivated while doing them.

Although these issues were present during the implementation of the materials, most of them were already expected since I had read about CLIL theory and its drawbacks during classes by the time of these lessons. Many of the possible ways of overcoming these drawbacks were provided by teachers as well as researchers in the CLIL-investigation field. Once students understood how to overcome some of the problems they faced, they learned how to implement the same problem-solving strategies in other materials or other instances during History-lessons. I found this to be impressive, since this knowledge will not only help them during my subject, but in other subjects of the Teaching and Translation courses as well.

These drawbacks during lessons were later overcome by reminding students of the learning objectives of the materials, encouraging them to use the target language and making an effort to put the subject-related vocabulary they used into practice. It is also fundamental to let learners know the learning outcomes of each lesson. This means letting them know what they will learn and understand about history, what they will be able to do at the end of the class, what abilities they will master and what attitudes they will build about teamwork. These are all important factors that were taken into account for the learning outcomes and goals (already listed in the information of each designed material). The learning outcomes were learner-centered as they focus on what the learners were going to achieve rather than on what me as a teacher was teaching.

The use of group talks was also essential to engage learners in constructing relevant vocabulary and concepts unique to history in effective work experiences with pairs or teams. These activities can be at word level, such as pairs of students classifying words into separate columns in a row, or pairs can ask and answer questions about life 200 years ago at the sentence level, for example. This solution to their frustration at the beginning of vocabulary-related activities was proven useful to win over students and solve any discouragement they might have had.

Another solution to students' frustration and constant code-switching was the scaffolding. This is an aid for learners to allow them to carry out activities or competences beyond their capacity. With History-related vocabulary or grammatical structures found in the materials, learners may not be able to create some structures within a single utterance initially in their language learning, but may construct them by engaging and communicating with another classmate.

It was a challenge as a newly CLIL teacher to implement scaffolding successfully in classes, as learners differed in the amount of help they required and in the duration of time the support was considered necessary. Some students required more help in some topics or context and for longer period of time than some of their other classmates. This cannot be taught to teachers, since it is a skill that teachers develop themselves depending on their students, context, subject and overall experience as English teachers. Nevertheless, practice makes perfection, and scaffolding along with the other teaching techniques and resources mentioned, proved to be successful in solving the difficulties this group of students encountered regarding the designed materials.

Regarding the benefits encountered, students' performance during the implementation of the materials met the learning objectives I had established for each of the materials. In connection with the learning outcomes of the lessons, by the end of each material students were able to have a general understanding of the topic of the materials, evaluate different opinions about the different ages described, give oral presentations, exchange information and opinions with classmates by pair and group work, make predictions before having all the information about a certain topic and analyze pictures and do gap-filling exercises. Moreover, they learned and revised through the Communicative Approach topics such as present and past tenses, comparatives and superlatives, prepositions, adjectives, verbs, adverbs and nouns and fundamental history-related vocabulary.

By the end of the materials' implementation, students were also able to practice a variety of learning strategies, either for reading and comprehension of a text, for enhancing conversation in the classroom by exchanging thoughts and results or for general oral presentations. Regarding the cultural aspect of the materials, students proved to have acquired an understanding of the culture of each period and the changing times throughout English History.

Overall, although each material presented a drawback to students when implemented, a solution could be found for each one. The benefits encountered when the designed materials were carried out in the online lessons met the expectations of the learning objectives and goals that the materials were designed for.

The drawbacks and benefits encountered in the design and implementation of these materials are exclusive of this group of students. It should be considered of great importance the factors and characteristics of this group, as they determined the results

of the implementation of the designed materials. For this reason, if these materials are implemented in another course with different students, the results may not be the same. The context in which this material was applied is very specific, as we should take into account COVID restrictions, the imposition of virtual lessons and the overall characteristics of this target group of learners. The results of these materials leave matters open since the materials do not determine how other students in other context will perform when they use them as resources. The main goal of this paper was the design of the material, it is left to each teacher and educator, whether a language teacher or English History teacher, the learning outcomes each material may have on their students when used.

Taking what was said above into consideration, it should be bore in mind that the results discussed proved the materials provided more benefits than drawbacks in aiding students with the topics chosen in the subject of English History. This entails a hopeful look at behaving similarly in other teaching contexts, however, as established before, it should not be interpreted that it will always behave in this way, having similar results for all context in which they are applied. Personal attitudes of students, where they come from, their social and cultural knowledge, their previous knowledge and attitude towards the subject, their age, the institution where they are studying, whether they are having online or face-to-face lessons, their teacher's experience, their competences and skills, along with other factors which are part of their own context, are characteristics which will affect the design of the materials as well as their learning outcomes.

For a teacher, creating a new lesson may be a thrilling proposition. A teacher may have been entrusted with designing a program for a subject she or he had a passion to study for a long time. Or for a key topic that requires a fresh approach, a teacher might be required to design new materials (not only with a CLIL approach in mind). Regardless of the situation, a teacher should bear in mind that one of the most important things is for students to understand the significance and validity of the subject at hand.

There are so many creative and useful technological resources and pedagogical techniques that can be used in the classroom that it can be difficult for a teacher to select which ones to use. There may be no right or wrong answer, but when a teacher makes her / his decisions, it is important to think of the specific group of students who will be taking the lesson.

Although one will (or may not) find an interesting topic to be the subject of a certain course, students will still have their own reasons to be there. They have their own motivations, lesson expectations, learning objectives, preferred learning competences, and overall personal characteristics. These factors will play an important role in the way the teacher will design the CLIL material along with the characteristics incorporated in each one. By allowing ourselves to notice and care about our students' learning, the implementation of the CLIL materials in our subject will probably provide beneficial outcomes not only for students' learning but our own teaching practice as well.

7. CONCLUSIONS

The main aim of this paper was to design communicative B2-level CLIL didactic materials which help adult foreign language learners in Paraná, Argentina, with their performance in English History classes. These CLIL materials were meant to aid students in their search to expand their linguistic and subject-specific knowledge and competences in order to be considered effective. It was also destined to bridge learning to a growing intercultural recognition of the subject they are exploring, this was expected to be achieved when implementing this material as a resource during the English History classes.

Although I had a lot of information about CLIL methodology, I did not have many references of case studies designing CLIL materials in order to know how to start developing these resources. Few research is done in the actual design of the materials, it is usually emphasized at a certain aspect of CLIL, whether it is teachers' beliefs, CLIL lesson frameworks, its objectives or various purposes. Furthermore, one of the main issues of CLIL is that, although positive experiences abound in CLIL literature, there are reports however, about their lack of context-responsive activities which are highly demanded in today's market. Over the last few years, there has been a great increase among educational institutions adopting CLIL materials to satisfy students' needs. However, few of those materials are designed for English History lessons or other subjects.

For the reasons mentioned above, at the beginning I found the design of the materials slightly frustrating personally and getting "stuck" in the design of some of the activities. Some days I had a clear mind on what I wanted to achieve with the design of the materials and found out helpful information regarding CLIL theory which was helpful in the development of the class resources. Other days I found out other opinions or ideas on CLIL which varied from the ones I read (since it is considered a brand-new approach, some research or papers are inconclusive on some aspects of CLIL or certain authors provide different opinions on what CLIL consists of), and other linguistic issues became apparent during my every day lessons with my students, which made me doubt on the learning objectives and design of my materials. For that reason, I revisited the material and re-designed activities various times in order to comply with the expectations and requirements I had from a start.

Although the process of designing CLIL materials was frustrating at the beginning, the challenges I faced became opportunities for learning and improving in what I understood

about CLIL and material design. It also made me look closely at what I was expecting my students to achieve, on how to draw their attention and motivation to the contents of English History and on the possible benefits that could come about from the implementation of the materials in class.

There were various specific goals I wanted to achieve through the development of this paper, one of them was to aid students in their understanding of the contents of English History and improve their overall use of the English language. I consider I succeeded in this task, since through the implementation of the designed materials students demonstrated great improvement in their knowledge of the topics, not only being able to comprehend them, but also contributing in the lesson with different opinions and comments about them, which demonstrated their interest and motivation when using the materials. Their use of the language, although with interference of the L1 or code-switching, was better as they engaged in negotiation of meaning, correcting mistakes, using vocabulary related to the subject and grammatical structures that could be found in the class resources.

Another objective of the design of these materials was for students to achieve or grow in their intercultural recognition of the subject which they are learning this year. English History provides a wide range of possibilities and opportunities for students to learn about English and worldwide cultures. I believe this group of students were successful in learning about other cultures from their own, as they gained knowledge about the values and customs during specifically the Tudor and Victorian Ages. These periods in time may happen in England, but have their own views and beliefs, their own cultures, as religion, the monarchy and its people were different. Through the assessment of the materials, students demonstrated they learned about these other cultures and also compared them to their own. This showed great progress in their understanding and tolerance of other cultures, along with their respect and also praise and criticism of their own society, values and customs. As a teacher of History these moments where class discussions can arise from students' personal opinions and motivation regarding culture are one of the most satisfying to encounter, since the communication with students is not merely to discuss specific topics from the English History curriculum, but to engage in topics which stem from these by students' own will and interest.

Further general objectives and their results from the implementation of the designed materials were discussed in the previous section. Formative assessment was conducted in order to briefly describe the benefits and issues I encountered in my lessons. By

looking at the results of this assessment along with the learning outcomes of students from the set objectives, it could be said that many advantages were found by the creation and implementation of CLIL designed materials. There were some problems encountered however, like students' frustration or boredom at certain tasks, or code-switching at the beginning of their use of the materials. Personally, I believe there were more benefits than drawbacks from their implementation, taking into account that most of the goals outlined were not only achieved but, in many cases, even succeeded my expectations.

Throughout my experience creating and implementing these materials in class, my personal advice would be for teachers to revisit and focus on their own teaching concepts and pedagogical methods that direct learning and teaching through the production of CLIL materials. I found out that once I defined clear objectives for each of the materials and learned more about my students' needs, the design of the materials was clearer, less time-consuming and enjoyable.

CLIL enables newly qualified teachers like me to play "a crucial role in developing cross-curricular elements of the national curriculum and/or contributing to teaching in bilingual sections in schools in the UK, Europe and beyond" (Funiber, 2016, p.42). However, while CLIL's teaching is directed at the assimilation of academic content into a language other than the native language, teachers must take into consideration the time and commitment needed to plan and improve CLIL materials based on this theory, while providing students benefits in terms of information and language acquisition.

Nevertheless, it may be too high a mountain to climb to introduce a CLIL approach to education, mostly because the teachers and students' linguistic competence may be lacking. In fact, a number of false assumptions, misconceptions and prejudices can cause some to believe that the shifting of the medium of instruction merely entails this approach. I have proposed in this paper that the introduction of designed materials based on an unformed and vaguely checked approach should begin with a reasonable understanding of the targets to be accomplished, taking into consideration the time taken to achieve them and the basic characteristics of each target group. The language skills of both students and teachers, as well as the curriculum to be taught, shall decide the particular steps to be taken in the implementation of the materials to be developed: the importance on the training of teachers in language and CLIL methodology, the preparation of teaching of the academic content and students' language needs, and the development of second language skills and competences of students. In order to

produce the required outcomes, committed teachers and engaged students need to be involved in the designed materials. In addition, university managers and leaders who understand the management and pedagogical values concerned should help them as well.

Regarding suggestions for further research, as mentioned previously, ongoing records of continuous, formative assessment should be done through observation of learning experiences in the classroom. Although the recording of information about each learner during each lesson is not necessary, over a period of several weeks, evidence of learners' progress as they work towards achieving the learning outcomes should be recorded. This can be done through the formative tools explained previously (observation, self-assessment and questioning) or with other means of recording information. This material was implemented according to the deadlines of the subject curriculum and the institution, taking into account students' schedules. However, it would be interesting to know other outcomes if implemented in a study or research which employs other assessment tools, resources, materials and contemplates alternative target groups (which may be bigger than twenty students).

A significant content insight may also be that of the learners. If there are further studies or research based on the learner's view on the use of resources in the classroom, it would be very useful to increase the efficiency of materials. For further investigation, learners as materials designers would be an interesting case, as the position of students still seems to be confined only to the use of materials, not their development. Learner-centered design of materials may better take place collaboratively in groups where more learning opportunities could be provided by representing each other's views of the matter at hand. Project work may also be incorporated in learner classes, taking into account that the final outcomes would not actually be learning resources but outcomes of the initiatives to be tested by the teacher. In general, it is odd that, at least according to the theory discussed on this paper and on a daily basis, considering the shortage of ready-made CLIL resources, learning by projects does not seem to be very popular in CLIL. Most modern learning philosophies agree on the fundamental role of the learner in the learning process, which means that students can often have a more active role in the design of materials. For older students, a fascinating study might be, for example, to assign the overall responsibility for material design of one unit or topic of CLIL History. Students would have to follow the learning outcomes under certain circumstances and perhaps afterwards there could be a contrast in the learning outcomes with those of a class where teaching materials were produced by a professor or publisher.

Another interesting line of research would be the design of CLIL implementing a Task-based approach rather than a Communicative one, like the one adopted in the design of these materials. Later, a comparison could then be made in the implementation of both approaches, Communicative and Task-based, aiming at evaluating the outcomes of both in classrooms which apply the CLIL methodology. Not only can the benefits and drawbacks in the implementation of both approaches be discussed, but there could also be research focusing on the actual development of the materials, discussing which approach teachers found easier to implement when designing the material, which of them was more time-consuming or what problems were recurrent in the design of the materials comparing both Communicative and Task-based approaches. In addition, further research could be done to get to know which of the approaches work better with the CLIL methodology. Of course, all these questions and projects should be investigated and considered by teachers or professionals who are passionate and motivated to do extensive research into a topic which is not yet developed or delimited in the academic linguistic and teaching community.

The experience of developing this paper and designing these three materials was of great benefit to my professional practice as a teacher and knowledge of teaching approaches and materials. Designing one's own materials may be intimidating at first, especially if it is ones' first time of doing so, however, most of the time it is what students need since some already published material may not fit what learners require in order to succeed in a subject. CLIL is a brand-new approach which has proven to be successful in many contexts, for that reason and because of the results I encountered when implementing these materials, I would encourage other teachers to create their own material. This is of great contribution to the English teaching community and may be helpful for teachers in bilingual programs, along with being beneficial to ones' own teaching experience and practice.

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9. APPENDIX

APPENDIX 1 MATERIAL: THE TUDORS

The Tudors

Activity 1: Look at pictures A – E and match them with the correct caption.

1. The defeat of Spain. ____
2. The ship of Sir Francis Drake. ____
3. England's expansion abroad. ____
4. The queen's progress. ____
5. The king on his death bed asks his son to uphold the Anglican religion. ____

Activity 2: After looking at the pictures above, discuss with your partner the following question: *In your opinion, what were the main problems the Tudors had to deal with?*

Activity 3: Read the text about The Tudors and then complete the spaces with the correct people.

A. Henry VII

The first King of the Tudor dynasty was Henry VII (1457–1509), who came to the English throne when the Wars of the Roses ended. His claim to the throne was shaky and there were frequent conspiracies he had to contend with. Through: a treaty with France, granting him recognition; a trade treaty with the Netherlands; and the dynastic marriage between his son Arthur and the Spanish princess Catherine of Aragon in 1501, he tried to strengthen his position. He strengthened the monarchy during his rule and transformed England into a modern state that he governed like a businessman. Henry aimed, through his foreign policy, to increase and improve the trading position of England. By - expenditure on shipbuilding so that England could have its own merchant fleet and expand its military strength, he also laid the foundations of English naval power.

B. Henry VIII

Henry VIII (1491–1547) was the second son of Henry VII. He was brought up in an almost entirely female household from his birth in 1491 until the death of his elder brother Arthur in 1502, with his sisters, nurses and his mother, Elizabeth of York. He was a renowned court figure from an early age, and he was a natural sportsman in his youth, which made him popular with both the English elite and the public in England. For both his natural good looks and his chivalry and education, he was dubbed the 'Golden Prince'.

In 1521, in appreciation of his Latin treatise defending the sacraments, he was awarded the title of 'Defender of the Faith' by the pope. Since then, English monarchs have kept this title and it is still on English coins today.

Henry married the widow of his brother, Catherine of Aragon, after Arthur's death, by special dispensation. Catherine had only produced a daughter in her twenty years of marriage, Mary, and Henry desperately needed a male heir to keep the country unified and powerful.

He began to consider marrying his pregnant lady-in-waiting mistress, Anne Boleyn, and applied for a divorce from the Pope to marry her. Henry broke with Rome and proclaimed himself 'Supreme Head on Earth of the Church of England' by the Act of Supremacy, as it was clear that the pope would not declare his first marriage invalid (1534). This meant that he had the power to nominate bishops, determine and enforce his will on the monasteries on articles of faith. The king soon abolished the monasteries, took their properties, and mostly vanished social charities, such as schools and hospitals for the needy. Another consequence of the policy of Henry was that Ireland remained a Catholic republic, marking the start of the Irish question. In 1533, Henry married Anne Boleyn and she gave him Elizabeth, a second daughter. However, she fell out of favour and was tried and executed in 1536 for treason, leaving the king free to remarry. In fast succession, Henry went on to have four more wives and one son, Edward, by Jane Seymour.

C. Mary I

In 1516, the only surviving child of Henry VIII and Catherine of Aragon, Mary I (1516–58), was born. She was a child, so her father was disappointed. As the divorce proceedings instigated by Henry increased, she reached her teens. Her father's rejection and her mother's harsh treatment had a fundamental impact on her life. As Henry also opposed the pope, her disappointment took on a theological connotation. She refused to abandon her own traditional faith and she claimed

herself to be the agent of a Counter-Reformation when she became queen in 1553. Her marriage to the Catholic Philip of Spain and the burning of Protestants, this effort to return England to papal obedience, gained her the nickname 'Bloody Mary' and alienated popular opinion. The end of Mary was tragic: her foreign and domestic policies were a disappointment and her country was still split over religion when she died, abandoned by her husband, without an heir.

D. Elizabeth I

Elizabeth (1533-1603), the daughter of Henry VIII and Anne Boleyn, became the queen of a divided country in 1558, most of which were anti-Catholic and anti-Spanish. She was twenty-five and had a good character, a vibrant intellect and a passionate personality. She had obtained an exemplary education and could easily speak French, Latin and Italian, but above all, she was a first-order political genius.

She faced the issues of marriage and succession, religious division, domestic frustration and international threats as a monarch. Her Church of England firmly returned the nation to Protestantism, and she allowed freedom of worship to Catholics. She was unmarried and used this as a political device, fostering the hopes of the princes of Europe with whom it was necessary to preserve good terms. She also reiterated that 'The Queen was married to her people'; this notion was gradually adopted by the people and started to make a cult of their 'Virgin Queen'.

To please her subjects, she wore magnificent clothes decorated with rich jewels; she went on to see royal change and to get to know her people. She had several drawn portraits and widely circulated copies. Literature, literature, drama and poetry have been influenced by the energy emerging from the queen.

Elizabeth brought peace and, at home and abroad, vanquished the enemies of England. As her key trade competitor and enemy, she recognized Spain. Open war was avoided at first, and discovery and trade abroad increased, making England a commercial and maritime force. In their piracy against Spanish ships, English sea captains, including Francis Drake (ca 1540-96), were secretly encouraged by the queen, and she took a share of the profits. They seized ships from America and Africa carrying precious metals, tobacco and slaves.

The Spanish decided to conquer England in 1588 and sent a great armada to the English Channel with 130 galleons. However, the Spanish ships were slow and heavy, while the English ships were smaller, quicker, and armed with long-range guns. The English were also helped by bad storms to defeat the Spanish Armada. Supremacy at sea enabled Elizabeth to lay the foundation for the empire of England, chartering seven companies in the name of trade to colonize.

* Pictures taken from Google Images.
* Texts adapted from Wikipedia.

A. Henry VII	B. Henry VIII	C. Mary I	D. Elizabeth I
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This King/Queen...

- A. Didn't have any children. ____
- B. Created the Anglican Church ____
- C. Was unpopular with his subjects ____
- D. Created the foundations of naval power ____
- E. Continued the Protestant Religion ____
- F. Encouraged the arts ____
- G. Affected the destiny of monasteries profoundly ____
- H. Married more than once ____
- I. Used pirates for national interests ____
- J. Used marriage as a political weapon ____
- K. Killed many Protestants ____
- L. Created a myth of the monarch ____

Activity 4: Were your predictions in activity 2 correct? What did you get right/wrong?

Activity 5: Get in groups of four and imagine each of you is a monarch. Prepare and give a coronation speech, you must include:

- What you promise to achieve during your reign
- Why the people in the kingdom should want you to be ruled by you.

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APPENDIX 2

MATERIAL: ELIZABETH I

Elizabeth I

Activity 1: Look at the portraits of Elizabeth I and discuss with your classmate: *How are they similar?* Take into account: lines, clothes, colors, where she is looking, and overall appearance.

Activity 2: Discuss with your partner the following question: *Why are there so many portraits of Queen Elizabeth I?*

Activity 3: Now look at the following picture. How does this portrait differ from the ones you looked at in activity 1?

Activity 4: Read the text about Queen Elizabeth I and choose the correct option (the options are in bold).

When Elizabeth I came to the **(1) monarchy / crown / throne / royalty** in 1558 after the death of her sister Mary, she needed the support of all her people. Monarchs used to make a **(2) travel / tour / holiday / voyage** of the country and show themselves to the people; this was called a 'progress'. However, Elizabeth had many Catholic enemies, and when it was not considered **(3) a safe / certain / sure / confident** for her to travel around the country, she chose, instead, to use **(4) statues / photos / descriptions / portraits** to show herself to her people and impress their imagination. Pictures of Elizabeth were copied and distributed throughout the land, and the nobility would have a portrait in their great houses as a symbol of **(5) loyalty / sympathy / kindness / friendship** to her.

The way the queen was painted changed over the course of her reign. In the early years, the queen was portrayed very **(6) majestically / colorfully / poorly / simply**, with little symbolism, or even

majesty, to convey that she was the monarch. Perhaps she looks like any other wealthy Elizabethan woman in some paintings.

The combination of the Renaissance style and the queen's almost mythical **(7) success / popularity / love / devotion** resulted in later portraits that are full of symbolism and are part of what has been called the 'Cult of Elizabeth, the Virgin Queen'.

The portraits give us some idea of the queen's physical appearance. While the **(8) tanned / sick / pale / healthy** faced woman with reddish-gold hair is common to all of them, it seems that every painter has **(9) held / kept / taken / captured** a slightly different image of her. We can be **(10) almost / not / but / rather** completely certain that her hair was a golden red, her eyes dark brown, her nose ridged or hooked in the middle, her lips rather thin and her cheekbones pronounced. Her hair was also probably naturally curly or at **(11) first / last / least / most** wavy. She may well have had freckles on her pale skin, but like all Elizabethan ladies she would have taken care to avoid **(12) taking / getting / reaching / shining** the sun on her face, and the make up she wore for most of her life would have protected her delicate skin from a suntan. In the Tudor era, white skin was trendy as it was what separated the rich from the poor. It showed that if a person had white skin, he or she did not have to labor outside for a living.

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APPENDIX 3 MATERIAL: THE VICTORIAN AGE

The Victorian Age

Activity 1: You are going to read about the “Victorian compromise”. What do you think is the meaning of “compromise”? In your opinion, why is it related to the Victorian age?

Activity 2: Read the text and check if the predictions you made in Activity 1 were correct.

The Victorian age was a complex and contradictory era: on the one hand, it was an age of progress, _____ **(STABLE)** and great social reforms; on the other, it was also characterised by poverty, injustice and social unrest.

The Victorians were great _____ **(MORALISE)**: they faced a large number of problems on such a scale, that they felt obliged to support certain values which offered solutions or escapes. Thus they promoted a code of values that reflected the world as they wanted it to be, not as it really was, based on _____ **(DUTY)** hard work, respectability and charity. These values were refined by the upper and middle classes, who had political and economic power, but they were of equal application to all strata of society.

In fact, one of the most important notions throughout the 19th century was the need to work hard. The idea of being _____ **(RESPECT)** distinguished the middle from the lower class. Respectability was a mixture of both morality and hypocrisy, severity and conformity to social standards. It implied the possession of good manners, the _____ **(OWNER)** of a _____ **(COMFORT)** house with servants and a carriage, regular attendance at church, and _____ **(CHARITY)** activity. Philanthropy was a widespread phenomenon; it addressed itself to every kind of poverty, to ‘stray children, fallen women and _____ **(DRINK)** men’ and absorbed the energies of thousands of Victorians, large numbers of whom were women.

Middle-class ideals dominated Victorian family life. The family was a _____ **(PATRIARCH)** unit where the husband represented authority and the key role of women concerned the education of children and the managing of the house. Victorian society was deeply concerned with female chastity, and single women with a child suffered the worst of society’s punishments: they were marginated as ‘fallen women’. Sexuality was generally repressed in its public and private forms, and being _____ **(PRUDERY)** in its most extreme manifestations led to the denunciation of nudity in art and the rejection of words with a sexual connotation from everyday vocabulary.

NOUN	ADJECTIVE
Stability	
	Dutiful
	Respectful
Comfort	
charity	
	Patriarchal
	Chaste
Prudery	

Activity 4: Now read the text again and use the word in capitals to form a word (it may be a verb, adjective, adverb, etc.) that fits in the gap.

Activity 5: Answer the following questions about the text:

1. What were the reasons the Victorians promoted a strict code of values?
2. What social classes perfected this code?
3. What was the code of values in the Victorian Age? Consider: family, work, sex and respectability.
4. How would you relate the word “compromise” to the Victorian lifestyle?

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